

H2020 DAEMON Project
Grant Agreement No. 101017109

Deliverable 3.2

Refined design of real-time control and VNF intelligence mechanisms

Abstract

D3.2 is the second deliverable of DAEMON's WP3, which builds on D3.1, and presents the detailed solutions to the research problems identified in the latter. WP3 focuses on near-real-time, real-time and in-network functionalities, and partially covers Objective 2 (Developing specialized NI-assisted network functionalities for B5G systems) and several KPIs in Objective 4 (Demonstrating the viability and performance of NI-native B5G networks), namely: (K1) VNF energy consumption reduction, (K2) Saving of computational resources at the edge, (K3) Response time of AI-based NI algorithms, (K4) OPEX saving, (K5) Reliability, or (K6) wireless capacity increase. For that purpose, this deliverable describes 13 NI solutions, two of which address two new problems (undisclosed in D3.1, grouped across the four tasks in the WP: (1) Compute-aware radio scheduling, (2) Multi-timescale edge resource management, (3) Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces, and (4) In-backhaul support for service intelligence. In this document, we first provide a high-level overview of their goals, how they fit into the global DAEMON architecture proposed in WP2 and how experiments planned in WP5 (which will be reported in D5.2) will validate their goals. Subsequently, each of these NI solutions is discussed in detail, including a mapping of WP2 requirements and architectural details. Finally, conclusions are drawn and future directions are described.

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	- 3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	- Fifth Generation
6G	- Sixth Generation
5G NSA	- 5G Non-standalone
5G SA	- 5G Standalone
AAR	- Application-aware RAN
AI	- Artificial Intelligence
API	- Application Programming Interface
ALU	- Arithmetic Logic Unit
AP	- Access Point
APN	- Access Point Name
B5G	- Beyond 5G
BS	- Base Station
BSR	- Buffer State Report
BSS	- Basic Service Set
CAWRS	- Compute-aware Radio Scheduling
CB	- Contextual Bandit, Contextual Bandit, or Code Block (depending on context)
CRC	- Cyclic Redundancy Check
CSI	- Channel State Information
CU	- Central Unit
CUPS	- Control plane – User plane Separation
DCB	- Dynamic Channel Bonding
DL	- Downlink
DNN	- Deep Neural Network
DU	- Distributed Unit
EAWVNF	- Energy-aware VNF orchestration
eMBB	- Enhanced Mobile BroadBand
FFNN	- Feed forward neural network
FR	- Functional Requirement
FW	- Frank-Wolf
gNB	- next generation Node B
GNN	- Graph Neural Network
IBSSI	- In-Backhaul Support for Service Intelligence
IMSI	- International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IoT	- Internet of Things
ISG	- Industry Specification Group
KNN	- K-nearest neighbor
KPI	- Key Performance Indicator
LCM	- Life-cycle Management
LLR	- Log-likelihood Ratio
LSTM	- Long Short-Term Memory
MAC	- Multiple Access Control Layer
MANO	- Management and Orchestration
MAPE	- Monitor, Analyze, Plan and Execute
MAPE-K	- Monitor, Analyze, Plan, Execute and Knowledge
MAU	- Match Action Unit
MCDM	- Multi-Criteria Decision-Making
MCS	- Modulation and Coding Scheme
MEC	- Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	- Machine Learning
mMTC	- Massive Machine Type Communication
MRT	- Maximum-Ratio Transmission

MSE – Mean Squared Error
MTERM – Multi-timescale Edge Resource Management
MVSF – Minimum Viable Subframe
NF – Network Function
NFR – Non-Functional Requirement
NI – Network Intelligence
NIF – Network Intelligence Function
NIF-C – Network Intelligence Function Component
NIP – NI Plane
NIS – Network Intelligence Service
NN – Neural Network
NO – Network Operator
NR – New Radio
OFDMA – Orthogonal Frequency Domain Multiplexing
PHV – Packet Header Vector
PHY – Physical Layer
PoC – Proof-of-Concept
PRB – Physical Resource Block
QoS – Quality of Service
RAN – Radio Access Network
RAT – Radio Access Technology
RIC – RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS – Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RL – Reinforcement Learning
RLC – Radio Link Control
RMSE – Root Mean-Squared Error
RNN – Recurrent Neural Network
RSM – Representational Similarity Matrix
RSSI – Received Signal Strength Indicator
RU – Radio Unit
S-ALU – Stateful ALU
SDN – Software Defined Networking
SF – Subframe
SINR – Signal-to-Interference-and-Noise Ratio
SLMANO – Self-Learning MANO
SMO – Service and Management Orchestrator
SMSE – Sum Mean Squared Error
SNR – Signal-to-noise ratio
SP – Service Provider
SRAM – Static Random Access Memory
STA – Station
SVR – Support Vector Regression
TB – Transport Block
TNA – Tofino-Native Architecture
TOPSIS – Technique for Order of Preference
TTI – Transmission Time Interval
UE – User Equipment
UL – Uplink
URLLC – Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication
V2X – Vehicular-to-everything
VIM – Virtualization Infrastructure Manager
VNF – Virtual Network Function
VNFM – VNF Manager

VR – Virtual Reality

WLAN – Wireless Local Area Network

Executive summary

This deliverable reports the progress made by DAEMON partners on the design and development of several NI-assisted functionalities targeted by Objective 2 of the Grant Agreement, with a focus on near-real-time, real-time and in-network functionalities. Eleven (11) B5G problems were initially introduced in D3.1. Two (2) additional problems are presented in this document. Overall, twelve (12) NI-assisted functionalities addressing problems across each of the four tasks within WP3 are presented in detail in this document: (i) compute-aware radio scheduling, (ii) multi-timescale edge resource management, (iii) reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, and (iv) in-backhaul support for service intelligence.

In more detail, Section 1 introduces the main results of this deliverable and explains their connection with D3.1 and, more importantly, their connection to the overall architecture described in WP2 (see D2.2). Sections 2 through Section 5 present in detail the design of each NI-assisted functionality designed across the four tasks of WP3. In addition to presenting their design, each section provides detailed information about their mapping with the requirements established in D2.2, architectural constraints proposed in D2.2, and their relationship with standardization bodies. To this end, each NI-assisted functionality is encoded using WP2-proposed N-MAPE-K representation to homogenize NI solutions proposed all across DAEMON and ease their analysis in the context of other NI-assisted functionalities and the NI plane in DAEMON architecture.

Namely, Section 2 presents NI-assisted functionalities in the context of compute-aware radio scheduling problems. Sections 2.1, 2.2 and 2.5 present in-network functionalities that operate in real-time to operate radio and computing resources in virtualized radio access networks. While the problem reserved for Section 2.2 is deferred for D3.3, Section 2.5 introduces a new problem (undisclosed in D3.1) and its solution. Section 2.3 presents an LSTM-based solution for the problem of traffic classification based on the evolution of Radio Link Control (RLC) buffers in radio distributed units (DUs). Finally, Section 2.4 studies the offloading problem of analytics tasks (such as image recognition) in the context of edge computing.

Section 3 groups all the NI-assisted functionalities in the context of multi-timescale edge resource management. More specifically, Section 3.1 proposes new edge service orchestration techniques by applying AI/ML models, taking into account the mobility of users that are consuming those orchestrated edge Vehicular-to-Everything (V2X) services. Section 3.2 proposes a Graph Neural Network (GNN) model to predict Wi-Fi performance in highly dense scenarios that use dynamic channel bonding. Section 3.3 presents solutions to address resource management problems with the goal of reducing energy consumption in an edge computing context. Section 3.4 presents the latest status of our work on data-driven resource orchestration. And Section 3.5 studies the problem of deciding, online and at two different time scales, the optimal amount of network resources' slices from the perspective of service providers.

Section 4 is devoted to the joint control of radio base station beamforming and Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) configuration. More specifically, in this section, we present a non-AI solution based on casting a non-convex formulation into a problem that can be solved with classical semidefinite relaxation techniques, which renders a solver that can be executed in sub-millisecond timescales without requiring fitting data.

Finally, Section 5 presents solutions to two problems, one of which is described here for the first time, in the context of in-backhaul learning. In more detail, Section 5.1 tackles the challenge of meeting a sub-millisecond latency for beyond 5G services by bringing intelligence at the Transport level of the (so-called) edge to core continuum. To this end, we show how to implement the inference phase of supervised classification in programmable switches in order to perform traffic classification. Then, in Section 5.2, we tackle the problem of backhaul circuit switching with the aim of increasing the speed and efficiency to better support the execution of a multitude of tasks, including network intelligence-related ones.

We complete the document with Section 6, which presents some of the NI-assisted functionalities described before from the perspective of WP2. This exercise allowed us to identify a set of new requirements for the evolution of the architecture of the NI plane introduced in D2.2. These requirements including resolving conflicts among functionalities operating in the same area in real time, coordinating monitoring resources effectively, and NI-plane intelligence (meta network intelligence) to select models in NI mechanisms efficiently.

We wrap up this deliverable with additional closing remarks in Section 7.

1 Introduction

Deliverable 3.2 reports the progress of WP3 towards achieving its main goal: the design of NI-based functionalities for (Near-)Real-Time Control and in-VNF intelligence. WP3 is specifically designed to pursue DAEMON's Objective 2, jointly with WP4, to develop specialized NI-assisted network functionalities that improve 5G performance, efficiency, sustainability, autonomy and reliability. To this end, WP3 does consider all the remaining objectives in DAEMON, which include the design of an NI-native architecture (Objective 1, focus of WP2), the establishment of guidelines for the design of NI functionality (Objective 3, focus of WP2), and the demonstrable achievement of a set of KPIs (Objective 4). In this deliverable, we provide an overview of the solutions proposed by the DAEMON consortium for problems introduced in D3.1 [1]. Moreover, in addition to introducing two additional problems (Sections 2.5 and 5.2) and their solutions, we map each functionality to the requirements and architectural design proposed in D2.2 [2] and analyze the interrelationship between some functionalities, which motivate a set of new requirements for the architecture designed in WP2.

This deliverable is organized as follows. First, in this section (subsection 1.1), we show and describe an illustration that depicts the overall picture of WP3 solutions designed to date, locating them in their respective network domains. In subsection 1.2, we summarize in a list of tables our analysis of the satisfaction level between WP2 requirements (as presented in D2.2 [2]) and the solutions presented in this document.

Sections 2 to 5 focus on the description of each NI-assisted functionality in detail, grouped into four categories that correspond to each task in WP3: Compute-Aware Radio Scheduling (Section 2), Multi-timescale Edge Resource Management (Section 3), Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (Section 4), and In-Backhaul Learning (Section 5). More specifically, each NI-assisted functionality is described according to four different facets:

- Requirements from D2.2: We analyze how the respective NI functionality satisfies the requirements presented in WP2.
- Guidelines from D2.2: We explain the methodology used, based on guidelines laid out in WP2, followed to the NI design.
- Solution Description: We explain in detail the solution provided by the respective NI-assisted functionality.
- N-MAPE-K representation: We describe the respective NI-assisted functionality in a homogeneous representation, as defined in WP2.

By following this structure, we ensure the traceability between WP2 requirements and architectural designs, and the detailed Network Intelligence being designed in WP3. We note that this document includes solutions that have been developed since the beginning of the project.

To conclude, Section 6 analyzes the inter-relationship between different NI functionalities. This analysis yields a set of new requirements for the DAEMON architecture, such as the need for a conflict resolution entity, or the need for the NI Orchestrator to exchange execution context information with the sibling MANO operating in the network for proper model selection.

1.1 Overview of D3.2 solutions

Figure 1 shows the big picture of D3.2 contributions, which are organized into three layers: **service orchestration**, **resource orchestration**, and **network function (NF) control**. At the bottom of the figure, we present all the micro-domains introduced in Annex I of DAEMON's Description of Action as DAEMON's high-level concept. The figure evinces that WP3 has designed functionalities that already span a wide range of *microdomains*, from the mobile backhaul to the new "Beyond Edge" domain. Note that WP3 has designed some in-NF control solutions, which are deployed within the virtualized infrastructure, as shown in the figure. These solutions aim at real-time operation and range problems related to radio scheduling or edge computing scheduling.

Each solution is represented in a format that includes information about the task in charge of the NI functionality as well as the section that explains the functionality in detail. In addition, the upper triangle includes information about the related type of KPIs addressed by each functionality (e.g., energy-related KPIs, operating cost-related KPIs, or network performance-related KPIs). Finally, in the right-most part of the figure, a simplified version of the N-MAPE-K architecture proposed in D2.2 [2] illustrates that different NI mechanisms are in charge of different network abstraction levels (service orchestration, resource orchestration, in-NF intelligence).

Overall, 13 NI-assisted solutions are presented in this document. Two address **service orchestration** problems at the edge from two different perspectives: energy-driven management (Section 3.3) and V2X-oriented management (Section 3.1). Below, in the **resource orchestration** layer, three additional NI-assisted functionalities optimize resource usage at the edge: WLAN predictions for spectrum

management (Section 3.2), data-driven resource orchestration (Section 3.4) and network slice reservation (Section 3.5). All these functionalities have been designed in the context of Task 3.2 (Multi-timescale edge resource management). All the remaining functionalities, designed in Tasks 3.1 (Compute-aware radio scheduling), 3.3 (Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces), and 3.4 (In-backhaul support for service intelligence) belong to the (near-)real-time arena of the **NF control layer**. More specifically, we present solutions for reliable Distributed Unit (DU) virtualization in Section 2.1, compute-aware radio scheduling in Section 2.5, O-RAN O-Cloud acceleration in Section 2.2 (details to be presented in D3.3), application-aware radio scheduling in Section 2.3, and task offloading in Section 2.4, all of which are designed in the context of Task 3.1. In addition, Section 4 presents a solution for RIS control (Task 3.3), and Section 5 two solutions for in-backhaul support for service intelligence (Task 3.4). On the one hand, the RIS control solution presented in this document aims at joint optimization of beamforming at the base station and the phase-shifting parameters of a quantized (realistic) RIS device. On the other hand, the in-backhaul solutions present functionalities to optimize circuit switching in backhaul switches with the aim of increasing the speed and efficiency to better support the execution of a multitude of tasks, including network intelligence-related ones, and executing machine learning (ML) models such as random forest classification models using the cost-inexpensive nature of programmable switches.

Figure 1. Summary and overall positioning of D3.2 main contributions.

1.2 Summary of requirements satisfaction by D3.2 solutions

Finally, we analyze to what extent the NI-assisted functionalities presented in this document satisfy the functional and non-functional requirements defined in D2.2 [2], showing clearly the relationship between the activities developed in WP2 and WP3. To this end, the following set of tables summarizes the requirements related to six clusters as defined in D2.2: RIS control (Table 1), Multi-timescale edge resource management (Table 2), in-backhaul support for service intelligence (Table 3), compute-aware radio scheduling (Table 4), energy-aware VNF placement (Table 5), and self-learning MANO (Table 6).

The methodology we have followed to document such mapping of requirements is as follows. Authors of each solution made a list of the requirements addressed by the concrete solution and provided a rationale for that (see subsections Requirements in D2.2 [2]). Editors analyzed these lists and proposed a mapping, which was revised by deliverable reviewers, task and WP3 leaders. The tables depict the result after several iterations in this process.

For each group of requirements (e.g., FR-RIS) we identify the section (the specific solution) that satisfies all the requirements of such group in columns (e.g., column S4). The last column (labeled D4.2) indicates if there is a solution presented in deliverable D4.2 that also satisfies a requirement. Each row refers to a functional (FR) or non-functional (NFR) requirement included in D2.2, using the same identifier. If a solution is working on fulfilling a given requirement but it does not meet it yet, the check is grey. For each requirement satisfied, we refer the reader for the corresponding section for a description of how the NI functionality solution meets the requirement.

Table 1. RIS control requirements satisfaction in D3.2 contributions.

			S4	D4.2
FR-RIS-000 DAEMON shall integrate Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) technology into mobile networks.			✓	
	FR-RIS-001		✓	
		FR-RIS-002	✓	
	FR-RIS-003			
	FR-RIS-004			
	NFR-RIS-000		✓	
	NFR-RIS-001			
	NFR-RIS-002			
NFR-RIS-003		✓		

Table 2. Multi-timescale edge resource management requirements satisfaction in D3.2 contributions.

			S3.1	S3.2	S3.4	S3.5	D4.2
FR-MTERM-000 DAEMON's Multi-timescale Edge Resource Management (MTERM) shall perform automated management and orchestration of resources and services in distributed edges and different timescales.			✓		✓	✓	
	NFR-MTERM-001						
	NFR-MTERM-002						
	NFR-MTERM-003						
	NFR-MTERM-004						
	FR-MTERM-004		✓	✓	✓		
		FR-MTERM-004.00					
		FR-MTERM-004.01	✓				
	FR-MTERM-004.02	✓					
	FR-MTERM-020		✓			✓	
	FR-MTERM-021				✓		
	FR-MTERM-006		✓	✓			
	FR-MTERM-007		✓				
FR-MTERM-007.00		✓					
FR-MTERM-007.01		✓					

Table 3. In-backhaul support for service intelligence requirements satisfaction of D3.2 contributions.

			S5.1	S5.2	D4.2	
FR-IBSSI-000 DAEMON's In-backhaul support for service intelligence (IBSSI) shall learn network policies using the user plane itself.			✓			
	FR-IBSSI-001		✓			
	FR-IBSSI-002		✓		✓	
		NFR-IBSSI-000	✓			
		NFR-IBSSI-001	✓		✓	

Table 4. Compute-aware radio scheduling requirements satisfaction in D3.2 contributions.

			S2.1	S2.4	S2.5	D4.2
FR-CAWRS-000 DAEMON shall integrate NI solutions in virtualized RAN systems			✓		✓	
	FR-CAWRS-001		✓			
		NFR-CAWRS-003	✓			
	FR-CAWRS-002		✓	✓	✓	
		NFR-CAWRS-001	✓	✓	✓	
		NFR-CAWRS-002	✓	✓	✓	
	NFR-CAWRS-000					

Table 5. Energy-aware VNF placement requirements satisfaction of D3.2 contributions.

			S3.3	D4.2	
FR-EAWVNF-000 DAEMON Energy-aware VNF placement (EAWVNF) shall profile the energy footprint of those network tasks that influence the network's global power consumption.			✓	✓	
	FR-EAWVNF-001		✓	✓	
		FR-EAWVNF-001.00		✓	
		FR-EAWVNF-001.01	✓	✓	
		NFR-EAWVNF-001	✓	✓	
		NFR-EAWVNF-002	✓	✓	
		NFR-EAWVNF-003	✓	✓	
	FR-EAWVNF-002		✓	✓	
	FR-EAWVNF-003				✓
		FR-EAWVNF-003.00			✓
		FR-EAWVNF-003.01			✓
	FR-EAWVNF-004				✓
		FR-EAWVNF-004.00			✓
		FR-EAWVNF-004.01			✓
	FR-EAWVNF-005				✓
		NFR-EAWVNF-004			✓
		NFR-EAWVNF-005			✓
		NFR-EAWVNF-006			✓
FR-EAWVNF-006				✓	
	FR-EAWVNF-006.00				
	FR-EAWVNF-006.01			✓	

Table 6. Self-learning MANO requirements satisfaction of D3.2 contributions.

		S2.3	S3.3	D4.2	
FR-SLMANO-000 DAEMON shall design autonomous and self-learning orchestrators and controllers that can operate with minimal human intervention.		✓		✓	
	NFR-SLMANO-000	✓			
	NFR-SLMANO-001		✓		
	FR-SLMANO-002	✓	✓	✓	
		FR-SLMANO-002.00			
	FR-SLMANO-003				✓
		NFR-SLMANO-001			
	FR-SLMANO-004				✓
	FR-SLMANO-005				
	FR-SLMANO-006				
	FR-SLMANO-007				

2 Compute aware radio scheduling

In this section, we cluster the description of NI Functionalities designed to solve compute-aware radio scheduling problems defined in D3.1 [1]. In addition, we present a new problem (and the associated NI Functionality) in Section 2.5.

2.1 Reliable distributed unit for virtualization

2.1.1 Requirements in D2.2

The mapping between the requirements established for reliable DU pipelines in D2.2 [2] is presented in the following table.

Table 7. Reliable Distributed Unit (DU) for virtualization. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-CAWRS-000	This NI Functionality introduces NI in a DU to attain reliability in vRAN systems.
FR-CAWRS-001	A predictive HARQ mechanism has been introduced in Section 2.1.3.3.1.
FR-CAWRS-002	A congestion controller has been described in Section 2.1.3.2.2 and in Section 2.1.3.3.2 to allocate DL and UL radio resources, respectively, given the computing capacity available in the system.
NFR-CAWRS-001	The simplicity of this NI's E-HARQ approach and congestion control mechanisms render inference time below 500µs.
NFR-CAWRS-002	This NI provides reliability when processing RAN workloads on virtualized infrastructure. By achieving such reliability, we can attain maximum spectral efficiency also in virtualized platforms. The performance of this NI solution in terms of spectral efficiency and reliability will be evaluated in D5.2.
NFR-CAWRS-003	This requirement will be validated in D5.2.

2.1.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The design of this solution has followed the guidelines established in D2.2 [2], Section 4.2.7, for predictive HARQ, and in Section 4.1.6 to design low-complex inference mechanisms that enable real-time operation. More specifically, the E-HARQ rule presented in Section 2.1.3.3.1 strictly follows the guidelines presented in D2.2 [2], Section 4.2.7. Moreover, the simple congestion control mechanisms devised to predict the amount of radio resources that may be processed in time, given an unknown computing capacity, explained in Section 2.1.3.2.2 and 2.1.3.3.2, follows the principles of low complexity mentioned in D2.2, Section 4.1.6.

2.1.3 Solution description

To overcome the issues introduced in Section 4.1 of D3.1 [1], we present a novel architecture of a Distributed Unit (DU), which we name Nuberu. Our solution is specifically engineered for 4G LTE and 5G New Radio (NR) workloads that are virtualized over clouds of shared resources with non-deterministic capacity.

Figure 2. Minimum Viable Subframe (MVSF) deadline for data processing tasks in a DU job.

Our design has one goal: to guarantee every Transmission Time Interval (TTI) a minimum viable subframe (MVSF) that provides the smallest set of signals required to preserve user synchronization, while maximizing throughput during shortages of computing resources. To this end, we decouple each job's data tasks into separate threads as shown in Figure 2.

- *DU forethead*: In charge of (i) building the MVSF; and (ii) coordinating the remaining DU data workers (middle of Figure 2),
- *DL-Data DU workers*: One or more threads in charge of the bulk of downlink processing tasks (processing the transport blocks (TBs) carried by the physical downlink shared channel, or PDSCH) (bottom of Figure 2),
- *UL-Data DU workers*: One or more threads in charge of the bulk of the tasks to process transport blocks carried by the physical uplink shared channel (PUSCH) (top of Figure 2);

and set up a hard deadline Φ_n for every job n (blue line in Figure 2) upon which an MVSF is compiled even if data workers have not finished. Note that, as shown before, basic MVSF tasks in charge of the forethead (such as computing grants or building PDCCH) require little or deterministic processing time, which can be estimated *a priori* to calculate $\Phi_n = n + M - \tau$, where τ is the time required to compile an MVSF plus the transportation delay (δ ms). The challenge is to decouple and adapt data processing tasks in a way such that the performance loss caused by computing fluctuations is minimized.

In the following, we first present the overall Nuberu design and then we detail the NI designed to address this challenge for Downlink (DL) data processing tasks and Uplink (UL) data processing tasks.

2.1.3.1 Overall Design

Figure 3. Nuberu: A reliable 4G/5G DU pipeline.

Figure 3 shows the detailed design of Nuberu. The forethead is responsible for building an MVSF and exploiting the work of data workers to maximize performance during shortages of computing resources. Note that, as a consequence of the MVSF deadline, Nuberu divides the time budget of each job into two phases:

Phase I: The forethead carries out the following sequence of basic tasks after the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) to process the received UL SF n and other UL-independent tasks to begin the process of building DL SF $n + M$:

1. (modified task) If UL SF n carries PUSCH, demultiplex UL TBs from the uplink control information (UCI) and hand over the coded TBs to UL-Data workers.
2. Process the physical uplink control channel and the uplink control information carried therein (PUCCH/UCI) if UL SF n carries it, and encode base signals (primary and secondary synchronization signals, (PSS/SSS)) and the PBCH for DL SF $n + M$.
3. (new task) Compute *temporary* DL grants depending on the availability of data, radio resources, and computing capacity. This is the first stage of a novel two-stage radio scheduling approach, which uses a congestion controller to issue temporary grants that may be processed before the MVSF deadline by a DL-Data worker. During quick computing fluctuations, some grants may not be processed on time and, to avoid dropping them and wasting resources, they are stored in a buffer for handling by the second scheduling stage of a posterior job (see Section 2.1.3.2).
4. (new task) *Snooze* up until time Φ_n (the MVSF deadline). This step is key to maximize the time budget used by data workers, yet gives the forethead leeway to generate an MVSF that preserves connectivity if data workers violate their deadline.

Phase II: The forethead awakes at Φ_n and invests the remaining $\tau - \delta$ ms in the following tasks to build DL SF $n + M$ before inverse FFT (IFFT):

1. (new task) *Early-HARQ* (E-HARQ) collects data from UL-Data workers that did not finish on time, and makes a *prediction* about the decodability of the corresponding TBs. This allows us to use *promising* UL TBs that otherwise would have to be dropped because they were not decoded on time (see Section 2.1.3.3.1).
2. (modified task) The second stage of our radio scheduling approach: given the finished UL-Data workers, the E-HARQ outcome, and the grants actually encoded on time, the final UL/DL grants

are computed by the MAC scheduler. Similar to its DL counterpart, UL grants are ruled by a congestion controller, detailed in Section 2.1.3.3.2. In the worst case, when no data worker finished on time (e.g., due to a sudden shortage of computing resources), no DL grants are allocated and the SF becomes an MVSF with the only responsibility of preserving user synchronization.

3. If DL grants are provided, the encoded TBs are modulated and mapped into the radio resource grid, and all the remaining control channels are processed.

2.1.3.2 DL data tasks

The first challenge is to schedule only the amount of radio resources that can be processed on time, and to buffer those that cannot be timely processed for a later job. We address this with a two-stage radio scheduling approach and a congestion controller.

Figure 4. Decoupling DL data tasks in a DU job.

2.1.3.2.1 Two-stage DL radio scheduling

As shown in Figure 4, we adopt a two-stage approach to compute DL grants.

In the *first stage*, Nuberu issues *temporary* DL grants as early as possible during each DU job's Phase I. Dedicated DL-Data workers then process (encode, modulate, etc.) the corresponding DL TBs in separated threads, and, when the task is completed, the worker stores the respective encoded TB in a buffer, as depicted in Figure 4.

In the *second stage*, during Phase II (after the MVSF deadline ϕ_n), the forethead computes the *final* DL grants based on those that have already been encoded and, hence, are available in the buffer. In this way, we can begin processing DL TBs as early as possible to maximize the time budget of DL-Data workers without compromising the budget of UL-Data workers, which needs to finish before allocating DL resources.

It is expected that the temporary scheduler issues DL grants such that the amount of work they require by the DL-Data worker can be carried out before ϕ_n , as illustrated in Figure 5's case (1). We achieve this by employing a rate controller that is introduced later, in Section 2.1.3.2.2. However, during quick computing fluctuations, the DL grants computed by job n 's temporary scheduler may be ready only at job $n + K$, for some integer $K > 0$. Therefore, K represents the amount of time that DL data is buffered in the vPHY, which allows us to absorb computing fluctuations appropriately, and hence, to preserve resiliency during events of computing volatility. This is depicted by cases (2) and (3) in Figure 5, which are DL TBs that could not be encoded on time, and hence, can only be placed into a DL SF in a later job. Not only do we attain resiliency with this approach, but we also increase efficiency compared to the baseline, which must drop grants that do not meet their deadlines, wasting resources.

Figure 5. DL temporary grants and DL congestion control with $\lambda = 1/4$ during DU job n . Delayed grants (in orange) can only be placed in a later job $n+k$, for some $k>0$.

2.1.3.2.2 DL Congestion control

Guaranteeing the timely completion of vDU jobs in non-deterministic platforms requires adapting the demand for (shared) computing resources to the instantaneous platform's capacity. **This is a fundamentally different paradigm to that of RANs using dedicated hardware, which allocate radio resources based only on wireless conditions and network demand.**

The temporary DL grants issued during Phase I generate workload for DL-Data workers. The processing time of the corresponding TBs depends on the amount of data transported therein as well as on the allocated computing resources by some task scheduler. Though allocating computing resources appropriately obviously helps, it is not enough to provide the hard guarantees we require. In the following, we propose a mechanism that adapts such computing workload based on observations from the workers' behavior.

Adapting a flow of requests (encoding) to a server capacity (computing platform) falls into the realm of *congestion control*. Hence, we resort to mechanisms amply used in networking protocols such as TCP. To this end, Nuberu's radio schedulers use a *DL congestion window* ($cwnd_{DL}$) that regulate the flow of DL grants. We adopt an additive-increase / multiplicative-decrease (AIMD) algorithm where $cwnd_{DL}$ increases by α physical radio blocks (PRBs) every DU job n ($cwnd_{DL}^{(n+1)} = cwnd_{DL}^{(n)} + \alpha$) as long as congestion is not detected or the maximum PRB capacity is reached and multiplicatively decreases by $\beta \leq 1$ ($cwnd_{DL}^{(n+1)} = cwnd_{DL}^{(n)} \cdot \beta$) if congestion is detected. Nuberu infers congestion if the buffer of encoded TBs contains $\lambda > 0$ times the vDU's PRB capacity or more.

Figure 5 shows an example where $cwnd_{DL}^{(n)} = 3/4$ of the PRB capacity and $\lambda = 1/4$ at job n . Accordingly, in this example the temporary scheduler issues three TBs, each with $1/4$ of the PRB capacity to fill $cwnd_{DL}^{(n)}$. The first TB, case (1), is encoded before the MVSF deadline, added to the buffer, and then immediately placed in DL SF $n + M$, i.e., it does not need to be stored in the buffer. Conversely, in cases (2) and (3), the respective workers did not finish their tasks on time. Consequently, the encoded TBs (once the respective workers finish) have to be stored for handling by a later job $n + K$ for some $K > 0$ (and hence, will be delivered in DL SF $n + M + K$). Because in this example $\lambda = 1/4$ and every stored TB carries $1/4$ of the vDU's PRB capacity, each item triggers a multiplicative reduction in $cwnd_{DL}$, as shown by the colored bars at the right.

2.1.3.3 UL data tasks

As soon as a UL SF arrives, the forethead hands over the (coded) UL TBs carried by PUSCH to idle UL-Data workers to decode them. The challenge, in this case, is to schedule UL radio resources that can be processed by the vDU on time (like the DL case), and compute UL feedback by the MVSF deadline for those that cannot. We address this with another congestion controller and with predictive HARQ.

Figure 6. Decoupling UL data tasks in a DU job.

2.1.3.3.1 Early HARQ

Both types of decoders managed by UL-Data workers in 4G and 5G employ an iterative algorithm to decode data, and a *stopping criterion* based on CRC checks to decide on the decodability of the TB. Then, based on such a decision, feedback is provided to the DU forethead, so grants for UL re-transmissions (or just new UL data) are allocated.

Like its DL counterpart, it is expected that UL TBs are often decoded before the MVSF deadline if computing resources have been provisioned appropriately and our UL congestion controller (see Section 2.1.3.3.2) adapts fast enough. However, due to the volatility inherent to shared computing environments, UL-Data workers may not finish their task in time Φ_n to provide feedback to build DL SF $n + M$. Simply discarding such TBs is a waste of radio resources. Moreover, the computing capacity has no impact on the decodability of TBs but only on the amount of time required to process them.

To avoid discarding UL TBs that cannot be processed in time, the forethead first performs Early HARQ (E-HARQ) after the MVSF deadline (ϕ_n), as shown in Figure 6, to predict the decodability of those TBs based on feedback from the workers. This prediction provides the required information to initiate Phase II, and avoids wasting expensive radio resources when dropping *late* UL TBs, which now do not have a hard deadline to be processed (demodulated, decoded, etc.). E-HARQ has received attention for low-latency communications. The approach is usually followed to design a stopping criterion for the iterative algorithms used by turbodecoders and LDPC decoders, or to predict the decodability of the data to send HARQ feedback early. As mentioned before, Nuberu leverages this technique to provide an extra time budget for UL workers.

Let $S_{w,t_n} \in \mathcal{S}$ denote the *state* of an UL-Data worker w at time t in DU job n , where \mathcal{S} is the state space of the decoder. At time ϕ_n , the forethead observes the state of each *unfinished* worker, i.e., S_{w,ϕ_n} for all $w \in \mathcal{W}_u$ where \mathcal{W}_u is the set of active UL-Data workers, and apply a rule $\Pi(S_{w,\phi_n}) \in \{\text{DECODABLE}, \text{UNDECODABLE}, \text{UNKNOWN}\}$ to decide upon the decodability, undecodability, or uncertain decodability of the TB. Once E-HARQ infers the decodability of the TB, it signals the UL MAC scheduler, so that it delivers the appropriate UL HARQ feedback to the users and/or schedules re-transmissions, accordingly, as *if the workers had finished their task*. UNKNOWN TBs are treated by the UL MAC scheduler as UNDECODABLE TBs; however, this information is useful for congestion control, as we will show later. If $\Pi(S_{w,\phi_n}) = \text{DECODABLE}$, UL-Data worker w is allowed to continue until a maximum number of decoding iterations wherein, as per 3GPP specification, CRC validation is used as a stopping criterion. Otherwise, the TB is discarded and the UL-Data worker w becomes idle again and ready to receive new work.

Our approach to design the rules Π and \mathcal{S} draws from different ideas in prior work on turbo and LDPC codes. The key idea rests upon the concept of *extrinsic information*, which spawns organically by *belief propagation* algorithms used by both turbo and LDPC codes. In a nutshell, belief information is encoded into log-likelihood ratios (LLRs), $L_b := \ln \frac{\text{Prob}(b=+1|\text{input})}{\text{Prob}(b=-1|\text{input})}$, where “input” refers to all the inputs of each decoding node i in a decoder, and b represents the information symbol (bit). The key to iterative decoding is the sequence of *a posteriori* LLRs of the information symbols, which is exchanged every iteration k between the decoding nodes of the decoder, so that each node takes advantage of the information computed by the others. To improve the bit estimations every iteration, the different nodes need to exchange belief information *that does not originate from themselves*. The original concept of extrinsic information was in fact conceived to identify the information components that depend on redundant information introduced by the incumbent code. Such extrinsic LLRs are used to transform a *posteriori* LLRs into a *priori* LLRs used as input in the next iteration.

Algorithm 1 E-HARQ rule $\Pi_{\vec{\gamma}}$

```

1: if  $K < 1$  then
2:   if  $\mathcal{P}(\text{MCS}, \text{SNR}, N) > \epsilon$  then
3:      $\Omega \leftarrow \text{UNKNOWN}$ 
4:   else
5:      $\Omega \leftarrow \text{DECODABLE}$ 
6:   else
7:     if  $(\bar{L}_{eD}^{(K)} < \gamma_1) \parallel (\bar{L}_{eD}^{(K)} - \bar{L}_{eD}^{(2)} < \gamma_2)$  then
8:        $\Omega \leftarrow \text{UNDECODABLE}$ 
9:     else
10:       $\Omega \leftarrow \text{DECODABLE}$ 
11: Return  $\Omega \in \{\text{UNDECODABLE}, \text{DECODABLE}, \text{UNKNOWN}\}$ 

```

Figure 7. E-HARQ rule $\Pi_{\vec{\gamma}}$

We implement a simple rule $\Pi_{\vec{\gamma}}$ parametrized by $\vec{\gamma} = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2)$ and detailed in Figure 7, that poses minimal overhead to the DU forethead. Note that, in case we do not have enough extrinsic information to make a prediction because the decoder has not completed any iteration, we resort to simple predictive models that only rely on SNR estimates.

2.1.3.3.2 UL Congestion Control

To maximize network performance, we need to generate UL grants that can be decoded before the MVSF deadline or allow sufficient decoding iterations to help E-HARQ make accurate predictions. Otherwise, these UL grants would have to be discarded, which wastes resources. To achieve this, we resort to another *congestion controller* that adapts the emission of UL grants to the availability of computing resources.

Similar to its downlink counterpart, we define a congestion window $cwnd_{UL}^{(n)}$, which bounds the number of UL PRBs that can be allocated to the DU's users. Again, we adopt a simple AIMD algorithm that increases $cwnd_{UL}^{(n)}$ additively ($cwnd_{UL}^{(n+1)} = cwnd_{UL}^{(n)} + \alpha$) when congestion is not inferred, and decreases multiplicatively ($cwnd_{UL}^{(n+1)} = cwnd_{UL}^{(n)} \cdot \beta$), with $\beta < 1$, when congestion is inferred. The obvious approach to estimate congestion from UL workload is to signal so every time a UL-Data worker does not finish before the MVSF deadline. However, this method does not fully exploit the predictive capability of our E-HARQ mechanism, which can infer the decodability of a TB well before explicit CRC confirmation. Conversely, our approach infers congestion every time E-HARQ cannot provide a prediction with certainty, i.e., outputs UNKNOWN, which occurs every time a UL-Data worker is unable to run sufficient decoding iterations before its deadline (see Figure 7).

Figure 8. E-HARQ and UL congestion control during a DU job.

Figure 8 shows an example of a job where PUSCH carries three UL TBs, one of which, marked in green as case (1), is declared decodable (CRC has been verified) or not (the iterative algorithm has reached the maximum number of iterations allowed before the MVSF deadline. This causes the controller to additively increase $cwnd_{UL}^{(n)}$. Conversely, cases (2) and (3) require the predictive ability of E-HARQ because they did not finish on time. In case (2), E-HARQ provides a certain estimation (decodable or undecodable), which also increases $cwnd_{UL}^{(n)}$ because the amount of work done on time is enough to let E-HARQ be accurate. In the last case (3), however, E-HARQ cannot provide a certain estimation because of a lack of sufficient extrinsic information and, as a result, congestion is assumed and $cwnd_{UL}^{(n)}$ is decremented accordingly.

2.1.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The algorithm presented in this section is not a learning one, meaning that it does not require continuous training on the data. After an initial analysis (detailed in D3.1 and D5.1) the model that was employed turned out to be a simple linear one, with a hard threshold depending on the iteration number. Therefore, we do not need any data preprocessing and no reward function is needed.

Table 8. N-MAPE-K loop mapping of the reliable distributed unit for virtualization.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors + Monitor	UL HARQ Feedback (i.e., state of completion of the decoding time, according to the number of iterations of the turbodecoder)
Analyze	N/A
Plan	Application of a linear model to detect whether the frame is going to be decoded or not.
Execution + Effector	Enforcement of the ACK / NACK message computed by the plan in the following DL Frame
Knowledge	Prediction state (ACK or NACK) for the different UL subframes
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	N/A (Linear model)

2.1.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

This solution is an implementation of an enhanced vRAN MAC and PHY system. Therefore, we consider for this solution the O-RAN architecture as the most suited and reference SDO one, as depicted in Figure 9. We refer the reader to [4] for more details about O-RAN architecture. The new pipeline proposed in this section is effectively a new implementation of an O-DU that takes care of the encoding and decoding capabilities at 5G MAC and PHY levels. The E-HARQ data (as well as all the UL and DL grants preparation) instead stays in the O-CU-CP module that is connected to the O-DU through the F1-c interface. This one needs to be extended to carry i) new data, such as the UL HARQ feedback that is fed to the O-CU-CP and ii) do that asynchronously, as we discuss in this section.

Figure 9. Nuberu and O-RAN architecture.

2.2 Cloud acceleration for vRANs

The solution to this problem, described in [1], Section 4.2, will be provided in D3.3.

2.3 Application aware radio scheduling

In this section, we describe another, i.e., a LSTM-based, solution for the problem of traffic classification based on the evolution RLC buffer, described in Section 4.3 of deliverable D3.1 [1]. In the present deliverable, the performance of LSTM is briefly evaluated and compared to the two other solutions proposed in deliverable D3.1 (i.e., K-nearest neighbors (KNN) and feed forward neural network (FFNN)). While deliverable D5.1 [3] assessed the detailed performance of KNN and FFNN already, a more thorough performance evaluation of LSTM will be provided in deliverable D5.2.

The performance evaluation is based on data that was captured with a traditional buffer acceptance mechanism in the bottleneck node. As future work we plan to repeat this performance evaluation with data captured when a new buffer acceptance mechanism, i.e., Low Latency Low Loss Scalable (L4S) is activated. Such a buffer acceptance mechanism aims to reduce the delay, and hence buffer occupation, and this may have an impact on the classification performance.

2.3.1 Requirements in D2.2

The mapping between some of the requirements established for self-learning management and orchestration (SLMANO) in D2.2 [2] is presented in the following table.

Table 9. requirement satisfaction for some aspects of the self-learning MANO.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-SLMANO-000	The classifier upon which the Application Aware RAN (AAR) scheduling is based operates without any human intervention: it is trained via a supervised learning technique, while the interference is operated without any human interaction.
NFR-SLMANO-000	AAR scheduling enables to treat various kinds of traffic (e.g., video, bulk downloads, ...) in such a way that they achieve their high-level QoS goals, which ultimately could be translated into human interpretable intents.
FR-SLMANO-002	Ideally, the AAR classifier allows fine-tuning the traffic differentiation based on class-specific intents (e.g., low latency for XR, high throughput for bulk downloads)

2.3.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The methods described in D3.1 [1] and D5.1 [3] and below are partially aligned with guidelines described in Section 4.2.1 of deliverable D2.2 [2], specifically on the ability to identify traffic on behavior rather than on deep packet inspection (knowing that most data is encrypted anyway). It turns out that considering time correlation is beneficial in classifying traffic flows based on observing the evolution of RLC buffer patterns.

2.3.3 Solution

In D3.1 [1] we proposed two classification algorithms to determine the nature (file transfer, video, web, radio) of flows based on the RLC buffer evolution (i.e., N consecutive samples of this RLC buffer, where samples are taken every 10ms): one based on K-nearest neighbors and one based on a feed forward neural network. In D5.1 [3], we presented a detailed comparison of both classification algorithms.

Here we present a third classifier based on LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory). The idea behind using LSTM is the following. The two methods used before see the normalized K -dimensional data sample that they use as input to base their classification decision on as a vector in a N -dimensional vector space. No particular importance is attached to how one entry of this sample vector relates to the next entry. The LSTM classifier assumes that there may be information hidden in the evolution of the RLC buffer (i.e., in the correlation of consecutive entries of the input sample vector) that can be beneficially used to make a better classification.

The LSTM-based NN that we propose consists of the usual input layer of N neurons, a single hidden layer of M LSTM neurons and a densely connected output layer of 4 neurons, where the labels 1, 2, 3 and 4 correspond to file transfer, video, web, and radio respectively. We split the ground truth data into training data (which consists of 75% randomly chosen samples from the ground truth) and test data (which consists of the remaining 25% of the ground truth data). As before, we use categorical cross entropy as the loss function and ADAM as the optimization algorithm. During training, we set 20% of the training data aside for validation. We train (with batches of 32 samples) until the performance (loss and accuracy) on the validation set no longer improves.

To compare the performance of this LSTM algorithm (with various values of the parameter M) with feed forward neural network and the K-nearest neighbors classification algorithm presented in deliverables D3.1 [1] and D5.1 [3], we calculated the conditional entropy in the classification made for samples in the test set given the ground truth label. If the classification were perfect, the conditional entropy would be 0. The conditional entropy can also be interpreted as the number of bits that would be needed to correct misclassifications.

Table 10 shows the result. It turns out that 80 LSTM neurons in the hidden layer yield the best performance and that the LSTM classifier outperforms the two alternatives proposed earlier in their best configuration.

Figure 10. Evolution of the loss and accuracy as training proceeds.

Table 10. Conditional entropy for various classifiers calculated on the test set.

Classifier	Conditional Entropy
Best feed forward NN (5 hidden layers, 80 neurons per layer)	0.240
Best K nearest neighbors (5 neighbors)	0.354
LSTM 20 hidden neurons	0.210
LSTM 40 hidden neurons	0.258
LSTM 60 hidden neurons	0.286
LSTM 80 hidden neurons	0.193
LSTM 100 hidden neurons	0.244

Table 11. Confusion matrix of the best LSTM classifier.

		Classified as:			
		File transfer	Video	Web	Radio
Ground truth	File transfer	0.998	0.001	0.001	0.000
	Video	0.002	0.840	0.158	0.000
	Web	0.002	0.040	0.959	0.000
	Radio	0.000	0.000	0.005	0.995

Table 11 displays the confusion matrix of the best LSTM classifier. This should be compared to Figure 11 and Figure 12 in deliverable D5.1 [3], which display respectively the confusion matrix of the best K-nearest neighbors' classifier and the feed forward neural network classifier.

A more detailed comparison of the three proposed classifiers will be reported in deliverable D5.2.

2.3.3.1 Future work

The analysis of the classifiers studied up to now relied on data that was gathered with a traditional buffer management strategy. Recently new buffer management strategies have been proposed that allow offering L4S throughput [5] to applications (e.g., Virtual Reality (VR)). With these new buffer management strategies, the evolution of the RLC buffer will be impacted. In a future deliverable we will plan to report on the impact of these new strategies on the performance of the traffic classification.

2.3.4 N-MAPE-K representation

Table 12 explains how the classifier maps on the N-MAPE-K framework.

Table 12: N-MAPE-K representation for the AAR classifier.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Monitor	The evolution of the RLC buffer is observed every 10ms
Analyze	The NN implicitly analyses the input trace. The values of the intermediate layers in the NN contain the output of this "analysis". As the NN is used as a black box, these "analysis" results are not interpreted.
Plan	N/A The classification result of the NN can be used for various purposes (e.g., accounting, setting the weights in scheduling and policers, etc.). For which purpose it will be used is not specified here.
Execution	N/A (see above).
Knowledge	The knowledge resides in the synapses of the trained NN.
Training Loss	The training is based on minimizing the categorical cross entropy on the training data (i.e., a subset of the ground truth data). Of this training data, 20% is used as the validation set. The training continues until the loss on the validation set starts to increase.

2.3.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The measurements in the RAN domain will use the generic E2SM-KPM, which exposes 3GPP-defined measurements while also supporting vendor-specific ones. In addition, the generic E2SM-RC will be applied to support the required mechanism. Moreover, after applying this NI, UEs need to be added/removed to/from an explicit UE list, which can be referred to the "CONTROL Service Style 8" in ORAN.WG3.E2SM-RC. This mechanism will be used to add/remove individual UEs to guidance policies after they have been detected as different application types using the designed NI.

In correspondence to our planned future work mentioned above, some standardization contributions are made to 3GPP. In 3GPP TR 23.700-60, a bunch of solutions is provided to address several key issues for XR/media services enhancements, and the conclusions of 5GS information exposure are reached in the technical documents S2-2207784 identifying three solution variants to move forward.

2.4 Compute-aware scheduling analytics VNFs

In this section, we present additional information about the problem and solution previously presented in D3.1, Section 4.4 [1]. To recap, we looked at the offloading problem of analytics tasks (such as image recognition) in the context of edge computing. We proposed an automated decision-making algorithm (which computes offloading parameters such as the compression ratio and under-sampling ratio) with provably optimal performance and constraint satisfaction. We specify next how the proposed solution adheres to the requirements and guidelines presented in D2.2 [2].

2.4.1 Requirements in D2.2

The mapping between the requirements established for compute-aware scheduling analytics introduced in D2.2 [2] is presented in the following table.

Table 13. Compute-aware scheduling analytics. Requirements satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-CAWRS-002	The solution jointly optimized the radio resource utilization (i.e., the decision variable that represents the time slice per user), as well as the utilization of computing resources (the frame encoding at the users' device, and the neural network input size). Hence, it fulfills the requirements of joint radio-compute optimization.

NFR-CAWRS-001	The proposed algorithm was proved to respect the reconfiguration time set by the user.
NFR-CAWRS-002	The proposed algorithm was proved to achieve asymptotically diminishing distance from the optimal decisions. Namely, the Regret is shown to converge to 0 with time. Hence, the algorithm fulfills the bounded distance from optimal requirement.

2.4.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The proposed solution adheres to the design guideline in D2.2 (Low inference time and energy consumption). This is guaranteed since the algorithmic steps that take place on users' mobile devices do not use complicated inference models, but rather only linear optimization and regular set operations (the neural network inference is performed on the edge server and not the user device).

2.4.3 Solution

The solution of this problem was provided in D2.2, Section 4.4.

2.4.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The following table explains how the presented functionality maps on the N-MAPE-K framework.

Table 14. N-MAPE-K representation of compute-aware scheduling analytics.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors	The sensing part of the proposed NIF solution is represented by the camera on users' mobile devices.
Monitor	The VNF software accesses the frames captured via the camera to make them available for pre-processing.
Analyze	In this VNF, the Analyze and Plan steps are intertwined.
Plan	The planning step is represented by computing the time slice window length, and the neural network input size (the two decision variables).
Execute	The execution in our algorithm is represented by applying the decided compression (encoding) and down-sampling (to match the neural network input size) to the captured frame and notifying the wireless interface of the mobile device of the decided time slice.
Effector	The effector is the wireless interface (e.g., WiFi) of the mobile device, which will be sending the frames throughout the length of the decided time slice.

2.4.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The provided edge analytics solution is aligned with the ETSI MEC (Multi-access Edge Computing) framework. The solution addresses how end-user mobile devices can intelligently share the access to an analytics service (Image Recognition) over WiFi in an optimal manner.

2.5 ML Radio Resource Scheduling for virtualized RANs

In this Section, we discuss an ML solution that increases the reliability of vRAN system (similar to the NIF discussed in Section 2.1), directly acting on the radio resource scheduling decisions taken at MAC level.

2.5.1 Problem description

2.5.1.1 Context

We focus on the physical (PHY) and the MAC layers of the 3GPP 5G-NR stack [6]. These layers take care of several functionalities, ranging from very low PHY level functionality (e.g., demodulation and decoding), to radio resource scheduling to UEs. We depict our model in Figure 11, and detail it next.

2.5.1.1.1 Model components

Our system consists of a set U of user equipments (UEs) u and a base station, which we will also call gNB, that provides communication capabilities to users. The UEs communicate with the gNB in order to transmit their information, according to the radio resource scheduling policies defined by the gNB. These policies are in practice translated into a specific amount of Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs) and a specific Modulation and Coding Scheme (MCS), which we will next present in detail. At each Transmission Time Interval (TTI), the gNB allocates an amount of PRBs and a specific MCS to each UE u for its data transmission, both in Uplink (UL) and Downlink (DL). We focus on the UL pipeline as this creates a major computing load for the gNB [7] and, as per Section 2.5.1.3, it is a key element for vRAN systems.

Figure 11. Decoding in 5G-NR: i) On congested CPUs: A deadline violation occurred and the DL frame was not generated in time; ii) On not congested CPUs: The grant carrying information in newTX or reTX is packed in the PDCCH of the DL frame.

2.5.1.1.2 Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs)

The total available bandwidth managed by the gNB is partitioned into N blocks, called Physical Resource Blocks (PRBs). Fifth-Generation New Radio (5G-NR) and Long-Term Evolution (LTE) systems use an Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) scheme for data transmission, encoding data allocated to a UE into a portion of such N blocks [8]. In 5G-NR systems, the number N of available PRBs is variable and depends on the total available bandwidth and the width of each PRB. For example, in a scenario with 10MHz bandwidth and 180kHz wide PRBs with a 20kHz guard band, there are N = 50 available PRBs during every TTI. So, at each TTI, the gNB shall decide on how to assign resources to UEs. Let n_u be the number of PRBs that are assigned to the user u for their UL communication with gNB. Clearly, it should hold

$$\sum_{u \in U} n_u \leq N,$$

i.e., the total allocated PRBs to all users must not exceed the total available PRBs in the system.

2.5.1.1.3 Modulation Coding Scheme (MCS)

Each user's u Modulation Coding Scheme (MCS) m_u belongs to a set $M = \{1, \dots, M\}$ of M elements, where each element captures a number of bits that will be encoded in each symbol transmitted by user u . For 5G-NR, 3GPP defines 29 MCS indexes, i.e., $M = 29$, ranging from the lowest BPSK capable of carrying 1 bit/symbol, up to 256-QAM that can carry 8 bits/symbol.

Combined with MIMO techniques, these MCSs provide the Gbps data rates obtained by 5G. The MCS that will be used by the UEs depends on the estimated channel conditions, which are upper bounded by Shannon's law. Thus, in practice, not all MCS indices are always available.

2.5.1.1.4 Radio Resource Scheduling Procedure

The UL radio resource scheduling is performed by a centralized agent in the gNB, e.g., the network operator, and consists in deciding the user u granted data for the UL channel at every TTI t . Periodically, each user u sends a Buffer State Report (BSR) to the gNB containing the user's UL demand, i.e., the size (in bytes) of the total data pending in UE's u stack. Then, the gNB schedules the user's u transmission and answers with a transmission grant for user u . The grant consists of two decisions: (i) the number n_u of PRBs that are assigned to user u ; and (ii) the MCS m_u that user u must use.

The choice of the granted user $u \in U$, and the selection of n_u and m_u depend on the specific scheduling algorithm implemented by the gNB, which uses information such as the user's data size or their channel conditions, e.g., their Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (SNR), that would limit the communication.

2.5.1.1.5 Transport Block Size (TBS)

The selection of MCS and PRBs eventually leads to a given amount of data that can be transmitted by a UE, which is called Transport Block (TB). Each TB has a specific Size (TBS) that accounts for the user data, the size of the extra information such as Cyclic Redundancy Checks (CRCs), and filler bits. Given the discrete number of PRBs and MCS, the possible values of TBS can be found using a simple deterministic procedure [9]. Thus, the TBS will be the main decision variable of the system.

2.5.1.2 Problem Statement

Virtualized RANs (vRANs) are a successful network paradigm nowadays, as they allow to decouple the underlying network infrastructure from the software-based implementation of a 3GPP gNB. Hence, vRANs have become a very important technology for next-generation mobile networks, also driven by associations such as O-RAN [6]. However, the operation of vRAN systems still presents some fundamental problems, such as the integration of hardware accelerators or the optimal interplay between the cloud infrastructure and the vRAN software. Here, we aim at maximizing the system throughput between the end users and the gNB, considering the possible impairments due to the cloud infrastructure. We take a step further from the direction identified in [10], and consider a learning approach.

According to the 3GPP 5G-NR specification [11], all the tasks that are related to uplink (UL) frame decoding (at the PHY layer) have to be completed before the next downlink (DL) frame is sent, as it contains information related to the ACK computed by the Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) process. This introduces a hard deadline for the completion of the decoding tasks (that are by far the most computing expensive of the full protocol stack [12]). In 5G-NR this deadline is configurable and let it be equal to $J - 1$ Transmission Time Intervals (TTIs). That is, the frame decoding result has to be ready before the ACK/NACK transmission that will take place in the J -th TTI after the reception of the original frame. In 5G-NR the value J is programmable, but the default values for the TTI length (i.e., 1ms) and J (i.e., 4) impose a deadline of 3ms to complete demodulation, rate matching and decoding operations.

A deadline violation has critical consequences on the vRAN operation, with sudden drops in the achieved performance, and it must be avoided by properly configuring the required computing resources. However, this is not an easy task in vRANs, where computing resources are dynamically orchestrated. Only with very high overprovisioning, which may lead to severely unsustainable systems, statistical guarantees of avoiding computing resource shortages are obtained.

This is needed because the usage of shared cloud computing platforms introduces the so-called noisy neighbor problem. Let different processes, e.g., different parts of the implementation of a vRAN system running on the same platform, share a computing platform. In this case, there may be capacity oscillations due to competing processes, which may lead the elapsed time for the completion of the task to exceed the target deadline. Observe that vRANs are extremely fragile systems when dealing with computing capacity oscillation: Missing the deadline, even for just some UL frames, can cause the UE to completely lose the synchronization, and hence the associated data flow. This would cause additional congestion, as the same packets will need to be sent again.

In Section 2.5.4, we propose an ML solution that jointly optimizes the UL scheduling decisions and the computing effort generated by them. This avoids disruptions that may be caused when the generated computing load is too high, e.g., due to decisions that impose computing-hungry operations at the same time. We next discuss the computing footprint of a vRAN system, and why it is paramount in a vRAN system to also consider the computing effort of radio resource scheduling decisions.

2.5.1.3 Decoding in vRAN systems

2.5.1.3.1 Decoding algorithm

In a 3GPP PHY pipeline, a new decoding task takes place at each TTI. Decoding tasks translate the modulated and encoded digital symbols that are received in the Physical UL Shared CHannel (PUSCH), which carries UL data, into bytes associated with each UE that are delivered to the higher layer of the gNB stack. After de-modulating the symbols and performing other channel optimization procedures, each bit belonging to the original transport block is decoded using an iterative procedure. During this process, each bit i is represented as a value LLR_i in the range $[-1...1]$, carrying the log-likelihood ratio of the i -th symbol being either a 0 or a 1. That is, the decoder processes a vector LLR of size TBS, containing the log-likelihood ratios for all the bits in the TB. When $LLR_i \rightarrow 1$, then likely $i = 1$, while $LLR_i \rightarrow -1$ means that likely $i = 0$. Finally, when $LLR_i = 0$ there is high uncertainty on the final value of the decoded bit i .

The decoder algorithm loops across all the LLR vector items LLR_i to maximize the likelihood of the received bits in the TB, and repeats the loop until a threshold likelihood ratio is achieved. After that, the TB is considered decoded and the CRC is checked, to discover possible channel errors. Standards define specific instances of this decoding process: the Low-Density Parity Check Decoder (LDPC) is used in 5G-NR systems and the turbodecoder in LTE ones. Both the LDPC and the turbodecoder share the generic iterative procedure that we described in this section.

2.5.1.3.2 Software implementations and complexity

The implementation of the procedure discussed above can be represented by two nested loops: an inner one that iterates over the LLR_i values, maximizing their likelihood, and an outer one that loops until the target likelihood is reached (or a maximum number of iterations IMAX). Thus, the time complexity T_{dec} of the decoding task is affected mainly by the following aspects.

(i) The TBS b_u as it sets the number of iterations needed to process all the LLR; (i.e., a larger TBS implies more iterations in the inner loop).

(ii) The relation between the channel conditions and the selected MCS m_u , that we will next explain.

The actual number of iterations of the decoding algorithm depends on the selected m_u and the experienced SNR. With low m_u and high SNR, the decoding ends with one iteration of the outer loop with a very high probability. Otherwise, more of them are needed up to the point that the selected m_u cannot be decoded under the given channel conditions, and hence even after IMAX iterations the TB cannot be decoded, and a NACK is sent to the UE to trigger its re-transmission.

Given the time-sharing nature of cloud systems, larger T_{dec} values imply a higher probability of suffering computing fluctuations (e.g., due to context switching). In this case, T_{dec} becomes less deterministic and thus less suitable for the frame decoding tasks. Figure 12 shows T_{dec} vs. TBS. It illustrates the elapsed time for full successful decoding, using the algorithm under varying channel quality conditions, and different competing loads (modeled by the variable β , which we will later introduce). Even when no competing load is present (red line in Fig. 3), the variability of T_{dec} increases with the TBS. This effect becomes even more evident when the vRAN system is competing for computing resources with others, and only a reduced amount of frames can actually be decoded within the default deadline of $J - 1$ TTIs, which in 5G systems is 3ms.

Figure 12. Decoding time T_{dec} under different SNR conditions and crowdedness factor β . Solid lines denote the averages, while shaded areas depict the 5th to 95th percentile.

2.5.1.3.3 CPU congestion

On cloud computing systems, such as those employed by vRANs, different execution threads share the same computing platform (i.e., CPU cores) to perform tasks. The element that is in charge of multiplexing computing resources among the different processes is the operating system CPU scheduler, which assigns CPU quantum to processes according to some periodicity rules (e.g., fairly sharing the amount of CPU time across processes) or when the process would not efficiently use the resources because it has to wait for the completion of another operation (i.e., upon an I/O operation or a memory cache miss).

To capture this aspect effectively, we introduce a congestion factor $\beta \in [0,1]$ that mimics the overhead introduced by other competing processes by slowing down the existing ones. This allows the decoding process and the number of competing processes to be described independently of the computing platform that is used, working with any CPU clock time. To indicate that there are no competing processes and that we can operate at a full CPU speed, we assume $\beta = 0$, while $\beta = 1$ indicates a very slow and crowded computing platform.

2.5.2 Requirements in D2.2

The mapping between the requirements established for reliable DU pipelines in D2.2 [2] is presented in the following table.

Table 15. ML Radio Resource Scheduling for vRAN. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-CAWRS-000	This NI Functionality introduces NI in a DU to attain reliability in vRAN systems.
FR-CAWRS-002	An intelligent radio resource scheduling algorithm is described in Section 2.5.4
NFR-CAWRS-001	The proposed algorithm takes place at every TTI
NFR-CAWRS-002	This NI algorithm maximizes spectral efficiency subject to the available computing capacity constraints. This will be validated in D5.2.

2.5.3 Guidelines from D2.2

For this solution we used the guidelines defined in D2.2 [2] in Section 4.1.6 to ensure the low-complexity inference mechanisms that enable real-time operation. When designing the solution, we used as a design guideline the minimization of the size of the neural network that takes the decisions. These guidelines, which are useful to meet the NFR-CAWRS 001 and 002 requirements, will be validated in D5.2.

2.5.4 Solution

We now discuss ATHENA, a deep reinforcement learning solution for computing aware radio resource scheduling in vRAN systems. Figure 13 illustrates the model of our system where two main functional blocks can be recognized:

- (i) The radio resource scheduler that assigns radio resources to the individual users, enforcing the decisions taken by.
- (ii) The ATHENA radio resource optimizer, which adjusts the above radio schedulers to the dynamic changes of the execution's environments.

Both the radio resource scheduler and ATHENA operate at millisecond timescale providing uplink scheduling grants to UEs.

Figure 13. The ATHENA architecture and its integration with the most important modules of the 3GPP and O-RAN architectures.

ATHENA creates a closed control loop taking scheduling decisions based on contextual information coming from the RAN, e.g., the UE-associated information and the decoding times achieved by the gNB implementation, and from the cloud provider's data center monitoring system, e.g., the current β . ATHENA then transforms this information into scheduling policies, optimizing RAN performance with respect to the hard time deadlines imposed by the computing platform. ATHENA employs Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques, combining trial-and-error from reinforcement learning, and allowing agents to make decisions from unstructured input data without manual engineering of the state space, as deep learning. We formulate our DRL problem with 1-step episodes, happening at each TTI. In each episode $t \in T$, the agent receives the current state $s^{(t)}$ as a feature vector drawn from a state distribution S , chooses and executes an action $a^{(t)} \in A$, where A is the action space, and receives a reward $r(s^{(t)}, a^{(t)})$. As stated earlier, the reward distribution over the $s^{(t)}$ is considered unknown *a-priori*. The result is a policy function $\pi(a|s): S \rightarrow A$, a stochastic function that maps the current states into a distribution of actions.

2.5.4.1 ATHENA DRL Components

2.5.4.1.1 State Space S

Let $s \in S$ denote the system state, where the state space S in ATHENA incorporates the combination of (i) the channel conditions associated with each UE SNR_u and (ii) the congestion β . The first variable is usually considered by state-of-the-art Radio Resource Schedulers, while the second can be estimated by the cloud provider metrics system. We define S as the context vector of the user's u space at stage t .

2.5.4.1.2 The action space A_o

As existing radio resource schedulers, ATHENA takes two consecutive decisions: First, an assignment of a number $n_u \in \mathbb{N} := \{1, \dots, N\}$ of PRBs across all UEs u . Second, a selection of an MCS over those PRBs, to match the UE channel conditions. Let $m_u \in \mathbb{M} := \{1, \dots, M\}$ be the MCS decision for user u , where M is a set of possible MCS that is available by the 5G radio technology. Thus, we define the action space $A_o := \mathbb{N}_u \times \mathbb{M}_u$, essentially capturing all possible pairs of decisions and allocated to each user $u \in U$ in decision episode t .

2.5.4.1.3 Rescaling the action space for scalability

In the configuration above, A_o increases exponentially with the number of users, as is evident from its definition. To avoid this, we compress set A_o to set A by using a mapping $f: \mathbb{B} \times \mathbb{M} \rightarrow T$, where T the set of possible values for the TBS. This reduces the cardinality of the action state to $\sum_{u \in U} b_u$, which is $O(|U| \cdot |T|)$, i.e., linear to the number of users in the system. At the same time, this dimensionality reduction keeps a direct relation with the decoding time T_{dec} (see Figure 13).

By moving from the discrete MCS, PRB action space to the TBS, we also simplify the ML task by making the action selection problem a continuous one, namely a regression one. That is, the outcome variable $a \in A$ is a continuous value \hat{b}_u which we discretize to the closest TBS b_u available in the standard [27]. This mapping is not bijective, i.e., "1-1". That is, a given b_u could possibly be translated into different pairs of $\{m_u, n_u\}$. In that case, ATHENA picks the pair that has the largest n_u component, to have a lower MCS and allow a faster LLR computation.

2.5.4.1.4 Reward function

Given the SNR_u condition for each user u , we reward actions a that will probably lead to successful decoding, ultimately pushing the system to learn allocations that result in high system throughput. Successful decoding happens when

- (i) the selected m_u is feasible under the SNR conditions, and
- (ii) T_{dec} does not exceed the deadline. Higher b_u values imply carrying more data. On the other hand, depending on the channel conditions and the system congestion, higher TBS could imply a deadline violation.

We design ATHENA's reward function to account for this observation. Our reward captures the contribution of

- (i) the data bits d_u^t that user u is granted by the gNB to transmit under the action a_u^t ;
- (ii) a binary variable crc_u^t denoting the result of the Cyclic Redundancy Check (CRC) of the TB after decoding it; and
- (iii) the decoding time $T_{dec,u}^t$ for the TB.

More specifically:

$$f(crc_u, T_{dec,u}, d_u) = \begin{cases} d_u & \text{if } (T_{dec,u} \leq J-1) \text{ and } (crc_u=1) \\ -K & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

where K is a constant term for penalizing wrong decisions. As we will discuss next, ATHENA learns faster because it takes advantage of both CRCs' values and decoding time.

2.5.4.2 ATHENA Internal Design

2.5.4.2.1 Actor-Critic design

ATHENA's RL architecture follows the Actor-Critic paradigm due to its superior scalability properties, as it can directly learn the best policy π instead of the reward r obtained by each state-action pair, and thus its direct applicability to the 5G-NR systems.

We opted for the Advantage Actor Critic (A2C) algorithm due to its ability to approximate the benefit of taking an action compared to the average at a given stage. The advantage $A(s,a)$ of an action a in the state s is defined as

$$A(s,a) = Q(s,a) - V(s),$$

where $V(s)$ is the value of the state s and $Q(s,a)$ is the value of taking action a on state s , following the current policy. The advantage in ATHENA's model captures the benefit of choosing an action b_u over an action a at given conditions $\{\beta, SNR_u\}$. The critic is responsible for approximating the functions $Q(s,a)$ and $V(s)$. In order to reduce the complexity of approximating those 2 functions, we replace the $Q(s,a)$ with the actual reward received by the environment $R(s,a)$. As function approximators, we use non-linear functions using the deep neural networks π_θ for the actor and V_ϕ for the critic and we perform the standard on-policy gradient update for the objective function J_θ of the actor-network

$$\nabla J(\theta)^{A2C} = E_{a_t \sim \pi_\theta} \left[\nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(s_t, a_t) (R - V_\phi(s_t)) \right], \quad (1)$$

and the minimum squared error for the critic:

$$L(\varphi)^{A2C} = (R_t - V_\varphi(s_t))^2.$$

2.5.4.2.2 Replay Buffer

In order to keep track of the collected samples, the master agent stores them in a replay buffer D , a structure that serves this purpose. When sufficiently new samples have been collected, the master agent performs a gradient update. While those samples are biased by the currently used policy, the agent also wants to imitate past good experiences followed by the older policies. To achieve this, it performs MSIL Self Imitation Learning (SIL) off-policy updates using old samples from the replay buffer with actor update:

$$\nabla_\theta J(\theta)^{SIL} = E_{s,a,r \in D} \left[\nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(s, a) (r - V_\varphi(s))_+ \right],$$

and using

$$L(\phi)^{SIL} = (R - V_\phi(s))_{\{+\}}^2$$

as the critic loss function, where $(\cdot)_+ = \max(\cdot, 0)$. Using those updates, the learning can benefit from samples whose reward r is greater than the current estimate $V_\varphi(s)$ and would encourage the agent to imitate past actions.

2.5.5 N-MAPE-K representation

The following table explains how the presented functionality maps on the N-MAPE-K framework.

Table 16. ML Radio Resource scheduling for virtualized RAN.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors	Probes in the DU and in the Cloud Orchestrator, to assess the current system load
Monitor	Reports of the SNR, BSR, and Frame Decoding Time
Analyze	N/A
Plan	Athena Algorithm that outputs mean and standard deviation TBS to be used for an UL user in the next TTI
Execute	Translation of the candidate TBS into a number of PRB and MCS
Effector	Interface available in the DU

2.5.6 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

ATHENA can be implemented in the PHY/MAC layer of a radio system, so we take as reference the 3GPP pipeline and the O-RAN architecture depicted in Figure 9. A scheduling decision is granted to a user u at a TTI t , the action is enforced in the PUSCH channel at $TTI_t + 4$ and the decoding result is collected at $TTI_t + 8$. This procedure is associated with one of the $|H|$ HARQ processes that the gNB and the user possess. This creates a problem for the learning architecture, as we are able to observe the system reward only with a delay of 8 TTIs. Hence the A2C network has $|H|$ agents that share the same actor networks so that the scheduling decision at time t is independent of the selected agent. More specifically, the agent $t \bmod H$ handles the decision at time t . In order to decouple the agents from the computing and backpropagating functions, we also designated a master agent. At every scheduling opportunity, the worker agent stores the sample as of tuple in the form of $\langle s, a, r \rangle$ in its internal buffer. At periodic timings, the master agent collects the samples of the worker agents, calculates the gradients, optimizes the model, and pushes back the updated weights. As depicted in Figure 13, the ATHENA components fit the O-RAN RT-RIC, O-DU, and O-Cloud.

3 Multi-timescale edge resource management

3.1 AI-enhanced edge orchestration

Given the emerging popularity of V2X services that came along with network latency and bandwidth improvements of 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) systems, provisioning of those services is mainly targeted at edge computing domains given their close proximity from the end users (i.e., vehicles). Thus, to deploy and maintain edge V2X services in a reliable and responsive manner by localizing access to virtualized network resources and services in the B5G ecosystem, there are some remaining challenges that need to be carefully addressed. Some of these challenges are operating under constrained edge resources, with strong resource heterogeneity, and in time-varying conditions. As such, these aspects are particularly important and challenging in the highly mobile environments with connected vehicles since V2X services require: i) continuous monitoring of network and computing resources, ii) efficient service reconfiguration, in the form of, e.g., fast scaling, redeployment, and migration, and iii) resource usage optimization. These requirements are setting some optimization targets that will make the B5G V2X system ultimately complex, whereas traditional MANO processes, which are either open-loop and inherently manual or closed-loop but slow and based on simple and static rules, need to be improved or even replaced with techniques that automate such MANO processes.

Thus, in this section, we focus on the efforts to improve traditional edge service orchestration techniques by applying AI/ML models, taking into account the mobility of users that are consuming those orchestrated edge V2X services. To do so, we present the features of an AI-enhanced orchestration framework together with the MAESTRO algorithm that optimizes the resource allocation for edge services that need to be efficiently relocated from one edge node to another in order.

3.1.1 Requirements in D2.2

The proposed AI-enhanced orchestration model fulfills the following requirements proposed in D2.2 [4] for Multi-Timescale Edge Resource Management, as shown in Table 17.

Table 17. Requirement satisfaction of the AI-enhanced edge orchestration.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-MTERM-000	Given that in network edge environments, services are deployed in a distributed fashion, the decentralized orchestrators that run on the edge should collaborate with each other, and consider the resource consumption across the edges to make optimal decisions on service placement. In particular, AI-enhanced edge orchestration leverages NIFs to improve the decision-making on orchestrating and managing distributed resources, and to apply decisions in an automated manner.
FR-MTERM-004 (FR-MTERM-004.01 and FR-MTERM-004.02)	To make decisions for AI-enhanced edge orchestration systems, or to perform model retraining, NIFs are constantly collecting data from various sources. The relevant sources, in this case, are computing nodes (resource consumption), network (latency, bandwidth), and application services running on the edge (data traffic, and application-specific metrics). Another type of monitored data considered when making decisions is the power consumption of edge nodes.
FR-MTERM-020	In the proposed solution, when the decision made by edge orchestrators affects different network edge domains, the centralized orchestrator needs to coordinate the decisions that different individual edge orchestrators make. Otherwise, edge orchestrators can autonomously make orchestration decisions that should be enforced on the edge service deployments in their respective domains.
FR-MTERM-006	The proposed solution for multi-timescale edge resource management leverages the help from NIFs to perform the orchestration of distributed service deployments optimally and in an automated way, thereby improving the quality of decisions and making those decisions in a more educated way by taking into account a comprehensive set of factors, such as consumption of computing and network resources, energy consumption, QoS measured at the client side (e.g., end-to-end latency), mobility of users, etc.
FR-MTERM-007 (FR-MTERM-007.00 and FR-MTERM-007.01)	This solution performs on-the-fly reconfiguration of edge service deployments, which are represented as chains of VNFs deployed on top of the NFV infrastructure. This reconfiguration means edge service scaling and relocation from one edge to another, which are the operations that have a goal to improve/maintain service quality.

3.1.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The solution for AI-enhanced edge orchestration is aligned with the guideline on Self-learning models based on dataflow programming, i.e., the data collection mechanisms are entirely based on the decentralized and distributed data management pipelines that deal with the data collected from heterogeneous devices (edge computing nodes, network probes, and on-board units from the vehicles). The Proof-of-Concept (PoC) that we designed for testing AI-enhanced edge orchestration using the Smart Highway testbed is heavily relying on the Eclipse Zenoh, allowing orchestration entities (both edge and centralized cloud) to collect/subscribe to data (monitored data, but also decisions) that are published by different actors, not knowing where these actors are located.

3.1.3 Solution

The distributed and heterogeneous nature of resources in 5G and beyond ecosystems imposes challenges towards traditional Management and Orchestration (MANO) systems, which are either manual or closed-loop but slow (i.e., not scaling well with service diversity and increased service usage in 5G.). To automate MANO operations and to make them intelligent enough to cope with the increased network complexity, NFV MANO systems need support from Machine Learning (ML).

Given the emerging popularity of vehicular use cases that improve safety for the automotive sector, more and more Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) services are created and deployed on the network edge (i.e., leveraging Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC)) to achieve lower latency, higher bandwidth, and larger reliability. However, these edge services require efficient management and orchestration to ensure their proper operation. To this end, the automation and intelligence of NFV MANO operations of such services will enable constant monitoring of network and service performance metrics, thereby automatically translating them to decisions that result in fast service re-configurations. There are some works that study the integration of ML techniques to NFV MANO operations, with the goal of enforcing operations and automating them [13]. However, there is still much to be investigated when it comes to realistic experimentation and testing the true impact of ML on the optimization of NFV MANO operations, as state-of-the-art work is either based on other optimization techniques (Lyapunov optimization techniques) that might be complex and lengthy for service management in V2X systems or their evaluation is based on the simulations. Therefore, we propose the enhanced Edge Service orchestration (MAESTRO) algorithm that makes proactive ML-driven decisions for edge service relocation in order to ensure Quality of Service (QoS) guarantees for V2X services, thereby automating edge service orchestration.

The MAESTRO algorithm we created is a hybrid edge service relocation algorithm, which is a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) algorithm based on The Technique for Order of Preference (TOPSIS) [14] and Support Vector Regression (SVR) [15]. The SVR model is trained at the edge orchestration layer, and it uses collected data to learn the interrelation between the infrastructure and service performance metrics, and to predict the average response time of a V2X service running on the edge computing. Furthermore, the model is used by the cloud orchestrator to proactively decide on whether the service relocation should be performed from one edge to another in order to avoid service disruptions due to mobility and low service performance.

3.1.3.1 *AI-enhanced NFV MANO framework*

Our NFV MANO framework consists of two layers, namely cloud and edge, which perform autonomous MANO operations, but enforce an interplay between them for managing orchestration decisions, or for retrieving data from distributed data engineering pipelines available in all edge domains. To enable the cooperation between different orchestration entities, certain management-level agreements need to be ensured, and more information about this type of agreement can be found in our previous work [16]. Each edge domain that consists of one or multiple edge nodes (i.e., MEC hosts) is governed by one edge orchestrator, which is, following ETSI NFV MANO framework, in charge of lifecycle management (e.g., instantiation, scaling, termination) of all MEC applications (including V2X ones). On the other hand, the cloud orchestrator is rather in charge of global optimization in the system, thereby making less granular decisions depending on the e.g., locations and density of vehicles on the roads for our particular real-life use case. One particular example of these decisions is service relocation from one edge domain to another, triggered by higher density of vehicles (i.e., edge service consumers) in one edge domain, by mobility, or by the need for optimization of resource consumption in MEC hosts across edge domains.

Two MANO layers communicate with each other in the two following ways: i) via Edge-Cloud reference point, which is used to either offload decision-making tasks between two orchestrators or to pass the already taken decision, and ii) via message brokers, which exchange data in a controlled way depending on the type of ML technique that has been applied in the system, thereby using that data to either perform training or model adjustments and online learning. Thus, depending on the time-scales of optimization (global or local, i.e., edge-specific), it is required that MEC hosts can connect data to ML models in a transparent and efficient way.

This intelligent NFV MANO framework is suitable for orchestrating edge deployments of V2X services that require low latency and high-reliability (e.g., service continuity enforced from the orchestration layer), as decision-making process is distributed, taking into account KPIs measured at the user's side.

In particular, applying ML to the orchestration of V2X applications enables i) optimized service instantiation, ii) learning utilization patterns for computational resources of virtualized network services, iii) prediction models for proactive resource allocation/relocation, and iv) optimized service relocation. However, ML techniques impose some additional challenges that need to be taken into account, such as vulnerabilities in terms of i) security, scalability, and transferability, ii) high computation power (not available in resource-constrained edge nodes), and iii) need for quality data to train the ML algorithms, as their performance on making decisions will depend on how close was the training data (e.g., synthetic), to the actual data used in production environments.

With respect to this last point, this work aims to provide initial insights from the design, development, deployment, and experimental validation of ML-based algorithms for MANO in V2X use cases using data from real infrastructure. In this way, we can close the gap between the data generated for training and the one used for the production environments. A crucial step towards enabling intelligence and automation is a robust data collection¹, which is then used for training, testing, and validation purposes. Thus, in Figure 13 we illustrate the data engineering pipeline that is used in the PoC solution built for testing and validating MAESTRO algorithm. The pipeline includes the following types of data sources i) infrastructure metrics (i.e., CPU, memory, and power, utilization), and ii) network-related metrics (e.g., latency and bandwidth). Data is being ingested into message broker instances in each edge node, and then processed by specialized helper services (i.e., MEC value-added services that perform data pre-processing), thereby making it suitable for further use.

Figure 13. Data engineering pipeline for AI-enhanced edge orchestration.

As illustrated in Figure 13, processed data is made available for retrieving data statistics, which might be of interest for the cloud orchestrator (data consumer) to get insights into edge infrastructure and edge service performance. Importantly, data is also exposed for training, testing, and validation, so that edge orchestrators (data consumers) can consume the generated datasets to train their local ML models. This is especially important in distributed environments where data privacy is fundamental, so the training is performed locally.

3.1.3.2 MAESTRO algorithm

Here we briefly describe our hybrid edge application relocation algorithm, the MAESTRO algorithm, which performs the selection of a new target node to which the observed edge V2X application deployment should be relocated in order to maintain/achieve the required service response time. It works in an automated and intelligent way thanks to the MCDM mechanism that takes into account various metrics, such as CPU, memory, and power utilization, as well as the predicted average response time for a vehicle client. The prediction is based on the SVR model that is trained at the edge orchestrator level. We use the TOPSIS class of MCDM algorithms, which is based on the comparison between all the

¹ As edge resources are scarce compared to cloud environments, it is utmost important to carefully monitor resource consumption through collecting data in real-time (resource consumption, user mobility events, QoS values). This data is used for deriving proper decisions e.g., to relocate or reconfigure service, in order to optimize resource consumption in distributed network edges.

alternatives included in the problem statement, and it is often used in solving large-scale decision-making problems in the automotive industry. On the other hand, we apply SVR, as a supervised learning technique, to find a function that approximates mapping from an input CPU load to average response time based on the training sample. Since edge orchestrators do not collect data from the other edge domains due to security reasons, they cannot make decisions based on an extended perception that includes NFV infrastructure managed by other edge orchestrators.

Algorithm 1: MAESTRO algorithm.

Result: Edge node selected for V2X application deployment
 Edge application A_i deployed at the edge node N_k , orchestrated by Edge orchestrator E_j Start;
 step 1; **while** V2X application A_i is active **do**
 Read KPI measurements for all edge nodes;
 Retrieve SVR model updates from Edge orchestrator O_j ;
 Prepare CPU data for prediction of average response time;
 Predict \bar{t} of A_i for all edge nodes $E_k, k \in (1, \dots, N_E)$;
 if \bar{t} during $\Delta T > t_{max}$ **then**
 Apply MCDM TOPSIS to make final decision for application relocation;
 Get decision;
 if Application A_i is already deployed on the selected E_k **then**
 go to step 1
 else
 Send notification about relocation to the source Edge orchestrator O_j ;
 if Edge orchestrator O_j accepts the decision **then**
 Edge orchestrator O_j sends request for proactive application deployment to O_{j+1} ;
 if O_{j+1} accepts the decision **then**
 Deployment on E_{k+1} starts;
 The state/metadata is being transferred;
 O_j generates notification for vehicle edge client to reconnect from edge E_k to edge E_{k+1}
 else
 go to step 1, add flag to O_{j+1}
 end
 else
 go to step 1, add flag to O_j
 end
 end
 else
 go to step 1
end

Figure 14. MAESTRO algorithm.

Table 18. Parameters for MAESTRO algorithm

Parameter	Definition
A_i	V2X Application, $i \in \{1, \dots, NA\}$
N_A	Number of deployed V2X applications
O_j	Edge orchestrator, $j \in \{1, \dots, No\}$
N_o	Number of Edge orchestrators
E_k	Edge node, $k \in \{1, \dots, NE\}$
N_E	Number of edge nodes
t	Response time
\bar{t}	Average response time
t_{max}	Maximum tolerable response time

Therefore, the local SVR model, trained at the edge orchestrator level by using locally collected data, is then shared with the cloud orchestrator. The cloud orchestrator predicts the average response time of the edge V2X application for the next period of time ΔT . If the predicted average response time does not exceed the t_{max} , which is the maximum tolerable response time for the edge application to provide a meaningful response (e.g., a credible record about the location and the estimated time of arrival of the firetruck from behind) to the vehicle client, there is no need for relocation. The threshold t_{max} can be defined per application type, or even network slice type, so that orchestrators can correspondingly adjust their criteria. Also, this value should be low enough to enable proactive relocation, meaning that the average response time will not be degraded in the meantime while relocation is being performed. Such an automated and proactive approach is in line with the level 3/4 of autonomous networks proposed by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) in [1], which refers to the

automated distinction between different kinds of services, thereby analyzing the service performance and (proactively) adjusting the service based on the changing conditions in network and infrastructure. If the decision is to relocate the edge application, the cloud orchestrator applies the MCDM mechanism using the predicted value of average response time based on the CPU load for all edge domains, as well as other collected metrics (memory, power), in order to avoid relocating edge application to an edge node that, e.g., experiences a high-power consumption.

Thus, at the the same time, the cloud orchestrator is making a quality-aware decision and trying to optimize resource usage in all edge domains. Following the steps provided in Figure 14, once the cloud orchestrator selects the edge orchestrator to be in charge of deploying relocated application instance, it sends the decision to the source edge orchestrator and triggers the relocation. If the edge orchestrator accepts this decision, it starts to proactively relocate the application to the selected target edge orchestrator. In the case of stateful applications, whenever an application instance is available at the target edge node, the transfer of state also needs to be performed before the vehicle reconnects to it. This can be done by applying the container checkpoint and restore technique [17], which involves service downtime. Otherwise, if there is no state but certain metadata (e.g., location and speed of the firetruck) that will be used to configure the application, then it also needs to be transferred. Once the context and/or metadata are transferred, the source edge orchestrator sends a notification to the vehicle client (as described in our previous work [18]) to change the endpoint of the edge application. The client on the vehicle side needs to be configured in a way to automatically process the notification from orchestrators and to apply the rule of configuring service endpoints. Afterward, the vehicle is reconnected to the target edge application instance, which is orchestrated by the target edge orchestrators. Finally, in case any of the edge orchestrators do not accept the decision made by the cloud orchestrator (as described in Figure 14), it adds certain flags to those edge orchestrators. Such flags should be further studied by the cloud orchestrator to learn about the reasons for rejecting the decisions, which should also help to retrain and reconfigure ML models.

Figure 16. Intelligent and automated management and orchestration system mapped to the real-life testbed environment.

3.1.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The following table explains how the presented functionality maps on the N-MAPE-K framework.

Table 19. N-MAPE-K representation for AI-enhanced orchestration.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors + Monitor	<p><u>Data collection</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compute & network resources • CPU usage • Memory • bandwidth • energy • KPIs measured at the user's side (latency, throughput) • User mobility (user's location, user's speed, mobility events retrieved from Core network) <p><u>APIs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edge-level orchestrator – Core network API used for retrieving user mobility events for users (e.g., in 3GPP Architecture for Enabling Edge Applications, this API maps to EDGE-2/EDGE-7/EDGE-8 reference points) • Edge-level orchestrator – User (e.g., vehicle) API to be used for retrieving periodic reports on speed/location, via e.g., C-ITS messages such as Cooperative Awareness Message (CAM) and Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM), and for KPIs measured at user's side (e.g., in the 3GPP Architecture for Enabling Edge Applications, this API corresponds to EDGE-1/EDGE-4 reference points) • Pub/sub mechanism (e.g., using Zenoh/AMQP/MQTT/Kafka) to be used for compute & network resources, and for KPIs measured at user's side
Analyze	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inputs are pre-processed so the dimensions of the inputs are reduced, and different inputs are given different priorities • two clusters of data, one that is used to perform fast relocation invoked by user mobility and the other used to perform optimization in the system (e.g., to decrease energy consumption in the system consisting of the edge nodes)
Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The edge orchestrator builds a performance function that maps the KPIs measured at the users' side, as well as the user's location/speed, with the service relocation action • This function is learned through interactions with the system • Data from users (i.e., KPIs measured at the user's side, and User mobility) and network resources collected in order of milliseconds, while reports on computing resources and energy collected with a smaller granularity, i.e., order of seconds (each second)
Executor + Effector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration with Kubernetes and Docker (distributed edge cloud with Kubernetes master and worker nodes, and Docker-based services) • Edge-level orchestrator performs i) service deployment in the selected target edge node, ii) application-context/state migration (if needed), and iii) relocation of service endpoint
Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database with the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitored data • Alarms for proactive service relocation • Performance function

3.1.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The AI-enhanced edge orchestration system that we designed, and deployed as a PoC on the Smart Highway testbed, is aligned with the ETSI NFV MEC framework. The AI-enhanced edge orchestrator from our solution embeds the functionalities of MEC Application Orchestrator (MEAO) and NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), and it interacts with Virtualization Infrastructure Manager (VIM) via Or-Vi reference point, and with Virtualized Network Function (VNF) Manager (VNFM) that performs Life-cycle Management (LCM) of MEC application services (V2X edge services). Both VNFM and VIM functionalities are covered by Kubernetes master node components in our proof-of-concept system for AI-enhanced orchestration.

Concerning the interfaces that enable User Equipment (UE) to communicate with edge applications and edge orchestrators, we refer to 3GPP SA6 group work on the Architecture for Enabling Edge Applications,

where EDGE-1 and EDGE-4 reference points correspond to the aforementioned interaction between user (vehicle client) and edge, respectively.

Figure 14. Reference architectures for AI-enhanced orchestration PoC; Mapping elements between ETSI MEC and 3GPP Architecture for Enabling Edge Applications, and highlighting the SDO blocks and interfaces that are relevant for the designed PoC.

3.2 WLAN performance prediction for spectrum management

In this section, we explore one of the most used technologies for Internet access in indoor scenarios, i.e., Wi-Fi. New standards, such as 802.11n/ac, introduce features such as Channel Bonding (CB) to increase network capacity. However, in highly dense deployments, the contention for medium access could be so severe, that Wi-Fi performance is severely affected by interference, causing problems like starvation. Thus, finding the best channel assignment in dense deployments under dynamic environments with channel bonding to reduce the interference between WLANs is of utmost importance. In D3.1 [1], section 5.2, we proposed a Graph Neural Network (GNN) model called ATARI to predict Wi-Fi performance in highly dense scenarios that use dynamic channel bonding. In this section, we summarize the solution and make a clear link with both the requirements and the architecture presented in D2.2.

3.2.1 Requirements in D2.2

The solution described in the following subsections fulfills the following requirements proposed in D2.2 [2] for Multi-Timescale Edge Resource Management, as shown in Table 20.

Table 20. Requirement satisfaction of the GNN model for performance prediction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-MTERM-004	The GNN will continuously consume the information gathered by a monitoring module in terms of spectrum usage.
FR-MTERM-006	The GNN model can be used by WLAN controllers/orchestrators to improve the quality of its decisions.

3.2.2 Guidelines from D2.2

Since the inter-Basic Service Set (BSS) interference is a problem that highly depends on the positioning of the devices in a WLAN, the described in the following subsection was designed to leverage the

information and relationship between variables that are embedded in the topology. Such a decision shows a clear improvement over standard machine learning (e.g., CNNs, FNNs and GB) and heuristic approaches.

3.2.3 Solution

In D3.1, Section 5.2, we looked at non-3GPP technologies, such as Wi-Fi, since future wireless networks will most likely be based on a combination of technologies that share the spectrum in a geographical area to cope with the massive internet demand of end users. For instance, one of the most recent standard-compliant techniques to enhance spectral utilization in Wi-Fi is Channel Bonding (CB), where two or more channels can be bonded to increase the channel capacity (i.e., available bandwidth). Nevertheless, addressing the demands of highly dense scenarios adds more stress to the already scarce spectrum, as more devices will fight for medium access. CB in crowded Wi-Fi scenarios might be counterproductive, as end-user Stations (STAs) might overlap. As a result, transmissions from multiple STAs may experience a high number of collisions and suffer excessive starvation [20]. This situation can cause drastic performance deterioration and increase the packet error rate. Using dynamic configurations of CB (Dynamic Channel Bonding (DCB)), where the number of bonded channels is adaptively changed depending on network conditions, is recommended to increase the throughput on the one hand (when the channel is not congested), and to alleviate the harmful effects of interference on the other hand (when congestion is high) [21]. However, it is not always clear for an Access Point (AP) which configuration to apply in a given situation of DCB.

To overcome the challenge mentioned above, we argue that performance (e.g., throughput) prediction/estimation could help in optimizing wireless networks by assessing the feasibility of potential system changes. Particularly in DCB, performance prediction allows Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs) to select channel configurations that minimize the inter-Basic Service Set (BSS) interference, optimizing the spectrum usage. To predict its performance, controllers or APs in a WLAN can use network models to assess how positively or negatively a given decision will impact the performance of the WLAN. Therefore, given a deployment (e.g., topology), a particular configuration (e.g., a set of channels that could be bonded) and the current state of the wireless links, the network model predicts the expected system throughput. In this way, optimization algorithms placed at controllers can have a reasonable network model to interact with.

More precisely, we built a network interference model called ATARI, using Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) given that interference can be modeled as a topology-dependent problem. GNNs are Neural Networks (NNs) that operate on data represented as graphs and exploit the relationship among nodes embedded in the graph's topology. We model a WLAN deployment, as shown in Figure 15. The links between STAs and APs represent the connectivity within the BSS through wireless links, while the link between APs represents the interference that BSSs have among themselves. As it can be inferred, APs form a mesh graph, while devices within the BSS form a star-like graph.

Figure 15. Example of a WLAN deployment. On the left, the topological view of the deployment. On the right, the graph representation of the deployment.

We compared the prediction capabilities of our GNN model against two Deep Learning (DL)-based models, a CNN and an FNN, and a Gradient Boost (GB)-based model. As a baseline for all ML approaches, we use a random guesser. The implementation details of the different models are given in D3.1 [1]. Figure 16 shows the mean Root Mean-Squared Error (RMSE) across all test scenarios' deployments in a given experiment for all the generated models and its standard deviation. The standard deviation in all models is very low, having a maximum of 0.66 in the FNN. As can be seen from the figure, GNN outperforms all other approaches in all defined experiments. The random approach performs the same, independent of the features used. Regarding the other ML models, it can be seen that learning from data represents at least a 20% improvement regarding the random approach, using all trainable features (E1). Focused on E1, i.e., the experiments with all features, GNN can obtain up to 64%, 56%, 55%, and 54% when comparing it against the random approach, the CNN, the FNN, and the GB, respectively. Surprisingly, GB performs slightly better in several experiments when compared to the CNN and the FNN. Despite its complexity, the CNN does not perform better than the FNN and the GB. This poor performance

might be due to data representation. CNNs outperform other ML approaches when dealing with high-dimensional data (e.g., images, time series). Even though the wireless environment is too complex to be modeled, the provided data do not include an extra dimension (e.g., time) that CNN can benefit from. For a more detailed version, we invite the readers to refer to D3.1 and [22].

Figure 16. Mean and standard deviation of the obtained RMSE by all models on the test data set.

3.2.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The GNN proposed above can be decomposed into the different components of the MAPE-K, as shown in [23] and in Table 21.

Table 21. N-MAPE-K representation for the GNN-based WLAN performance predictor.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors + Monitor	Link State composed of the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), and the received signal strength indicator (RSSI). The AP's available channel configurations, distance and associations among users and APs, users' traffic demands.
Analyze	Inputs are converted into a graph-like structure to capture all the topological properties of the WLAN deployment.
Plan	A GNN to predict the throughput at each client and AP.
Execution + Effector	The predictor can be part of a digital twin and be used by a WLAN controller to solve the WLAN channel bonding optimization problem.
Knowledge	Monitored data, current setup, best performance prediction, possible channel configurations, and learned channel configuration selection policy.
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	Loss Function: Root Mean-Squared Error.

3.2.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The model described in the previous subsections aligns well with the ITU architectural framework for machine learning in future networks, including IMT-2020 [24]. The GNN model can be used as an interference management application in futuristic Software Defined WLANs (SD-WLAN), as depicted in Figure 17. First, different measurements are constantly collected via the collector block. These measurements might come from the terminals connected to the WLAN, but also from the WLAN's data plane (e.g., transmission capabilities and sensed interference). They also constitute the source of data (SRC). The collected measurements are later aggregated in the pre-producer block and compose the network state. Here, a graph-like structure is also created, so the GNN receives a data structure ready to operate on. Afterward, the model produces the expected WLAN performance under the given circumstances, which are then used on the controller side to create channel configuration policies. The decisions from the controller are distributed to the different access points through an appropriate API, so they configure the channels according to the controller's decisions.

Figure 17. ATARI and ITU reference architecture.

3.3 Energy aware edge resource management

In this section, we are going to focus on those solutions that address resource management with the goal of reducing energy consumption in an edge computing context.

3.3.1 Requirements in D2.2

In this subsection, we include a table with a mapping between the requirements described in D2.2 [2] for Multi-Timescale Edge Resource Management (Task 3.2). We will address mainly the requirements defined in EAWVNF (Energy-Aware VNF Control & Orchestration) for the edge context, concretely, eight functional requirements and three non-functional requirements. Also, one of the modules described here addresses one functional requirement related to SLMANO (Self-Learning MANO).

Table 22. Energy-aware edge resource management. Requirements satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-EAWVNF-000	The first thing we have done to meet the goal of energy efficiency is to identify the list of elements that strongly affect the energy consumption in the edge context. We have implemented the SAVRUS algorithm that works with unknown-domain (in this case, VNFs for edge-based mobile networks) to identify and rank the main network features and their interactions by how much they affect the final energy consumption. See D3.1, Section 5.3.2.1
FR-EAWVNF-001.01	Our energy consumption model (UMA_EM) calculates the energy footprint of VNFs in terms of CPU data transmission according to the node in which VNFs are deployed.
FR-EAWVNF-002	The modules presented in our solution consider hardware resource usage parameters (e.g., CPU, network card, etc.) in the calculation of the energy footprint
FR-SLMANO-002.00	The CQL framework supports advanced optimization by supporting multi-objective combinations of quality attributes, such as latency and energy consumption.
NFR-EAWVNF-001	The SAVRUS algorithm and the CQL framework have proven to scale to an energy-measured search space of 10 million, while considering the heterogeneity of devices typically found on the edge.
NFR-EAWVNF-002	The CQL framework supports an energy-aware search of near-optimal placements of VNFs.
NFR-EAWVNF-003	The models and frameworks rely on sampling for high-speed and efficient analyses, hence theoretically requiring less energy than the optimization offered.

3.3.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The domain-agnostic SAVRUS algorithm was detailed in D3.1, Section 5.3.2.1, and it is the first step in uncovering which components of a network running VNFs are the culprit of affecting the rate of consumed energy. The results provide a solid reference point for accurate variability and energy models.

The CQL framework detailed in the next section has been developed to be expressive and flexible enough to represent the merge of the generated variability and energy models with the quality models. This solution integrates the QoS and its requirements within the network description.

Since an NI model's computational complexity strongly correlates with its latency performance and energy consumption, our AVA and NDF modules, introduced in the next section and presented in detail in D3.1 (Section 5.3.3), have been designed to have low complexity. To support this claim and evaluate their scalability, the execution times for different problem sizes have been evaluated using a benchmark version of the AVA and NDF modules (D3.1, Section 5.3.3.1).

Finally, the CQL framework supports advanced weighted multi-objective reasoning performed by virtual network experts, who can define personalized queries to the integrated model. This reasoning and its scalability are evaluated and compared against the previous state-of-the-art for 5 various large systems, including VNFs at the edge. We prove that reasoning runtimes are sufficiently fast for the industry, the energy expenditure is minimal, and the results are competent enough to claim that our CQL framework is worth applying.

3.3.3 Solution

3.3.3.1 SAVRUS Module

In Section 5.3.2.1 of D3.1, we defined and evaluated SAVRUS, a domain-unknown algorithm to uncover the noteworthy features and components of VNFs in the Edge. In summary, SAVRUS is a lineal process that applies *Transfer Learned Statistical Sampling*, *K-nearest neighbors' prediction*, *Pair-Wise Mann Whitney U test*, and *Statistical Triple-Wise analysis*. It was tested by modeling and analyzing 5 Edge Computing systems for the energy consumption rate of their virtualized functions and heterogeneous devices.

SAVRUS results were considered while building the integrated variability, energy, and quality models. We develop the Categorical Query Language Models for VNF SPLs at the Edge to support that integration. Figure 18 is an example of one of our integrated models, a reduced version of our case study Virtual Network System in the Edge. As shown, it integrates VNFs, software and hardware noteworthy components, and different types of quality attributes modeled at different levels. Feature-wise, we find Dependency, Usability, and Security; variant-wise, we find Performance in Seconds and Energy in Joules.

Figure 18. Reduced version of a typical Virtual Network System in the Edge.

3.3.3.2 AVA and NDF modules

In D3.1 (Section 5.3.3), we analyze the configuration of the VNF requirements and edge-based infrastructure capabilities to improve energy consumption estimation. Concretely, the proposed solutions support: (i) resource estimation based on hardware demand, identifying those that strongly affect energy consumption on mobile networks; (ii) the adaptation of VNFs resource requirements to the available Edge resources, trying to allocate the least quantity of resources that fits VNFs demands; and (iii) the discovery of new nodes meeting VNFs resource demands, if the available resources in the current infrastructure are not enough to provide a specific QoS required by VNFs.

The energy consumption of applications (including VNFs) can be differentiated into two main parts in the context of mobile networks (i): computational and communication energy consumption. For wireless communications, the factors usually considered as part of energy consumption are the power transmission, the transmission rate, and the amount of data to be transmitted. In computation, the CPU is the most influential factor, involving the CPU power and consumption on the node's side and the number of cycles/instructions on the application side. Thus, these are the values on which our energy model *UMA_EM* is mainly based (more details in D4.1, Section 3.1.3.2).

Regarding the adaptation of VNFs resource requirements to the available Edge resources (ii), the solution proposed was the Application Variability Adaptor (AVA). As an input configuration of VNF and a given infrastructure, the algorithm output allows the identification of service functions with special requirements in terms of infrastructure components.

Concerning the discovery of new nodes meeting VNFs resource demands (iii), the solution proposed is the New Devices Finder (NDF), which is required when service must be provided that is not currently supported by the infrastructure, i.e., the infrastructure must support features that are not currently supported.

3.3.3.3 CQL framework for QoS optimization

We develop the CQL framework graphically summarized for very advanced querying and searching. This framework allows very complex queries involving the same time regular components, numerical components, feature and variant-wise interactions, weighted search, and domain fusion. For example, a new domain-weighted multi-objective optimization query evaluated is the objective:

Minimize: 0.7 Cost, 0.3 Energy Rate (dynamically calculated as Energy ÷ Latency)

Figure 19. CQL framework for VNFs reasoning at the Edge.

It is built using our merged model and over the CQL IDE tool – the Category Theory (CT) state-of-the-art Integrated Development Editor. Besides currently allowing complex reasoning, the main advantage of our CQL framework is its flexibility and speed. The flexibility is due to the intrinsic query composition of CT algebra, where we define a set of minimum queries which can be reused to form the complex ones. For example, Random Sampling is decomposed as Random Space Generation and sub-space filtering. On the other hand, speed comes from the ability of CT to use any reasoner concurrently, prioritizing the ones that perform better for each step in a query. In our case, we use a combination of an automated theorem prover with Knuth-Bendix completion for logic and equations, hashing, balanced trees, and chasing for data-type and cross-object arrows. We evaluated the CQL framework for various complex queries over 5 different systems related to VNFs in the Edge. The considered systems are described as follows in Figure 20.

Part of the evaluation was also to double-check the results, if possible, and to compare the scalability with the previous state-of-the-art reasoning tools: ClaferMoo, FLAMA framework, and SATIBEA.

In summary, even for the most complex system and query, to weightily optimize *FullVNS* with a measured space size of 10 million, our CQL framework finished the task in a few minutes. The CQL framework reasoning takes less than a second for smaller spaces and lesser tasks.

SPL	Description	Features	Constraints	Configurations	Quality Attributes
<i>Pizza</i>	Italian vendor machine [28]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 12 • Numerical: 1 	<i>Empty</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 42 • Measured: 84 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Cost $\in (5,25)$ \$: Function: Addition • Configuration level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (2) Time $\in (1,10^3)$ seconds
<i>Truck</i>	Truck factory [45]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 33 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 10 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 234 • Measured: 234 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Size $\in [0,10]$ metres²: Function: Product
<i>JHipster</i>	Software generator [24]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 45 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 13 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 26,256 • Measured: 105,024 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Usability $\in (0, 10)$: Function: Addition (2) Battery $\in (0, 20)$: Function: Addition (3) Footprint $\in (0, 10)$: Function: Addition • Configuration level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (4) Compileable $\in [true, false]$
(1) <i>VNS</i> and (2) <i>FullVNS</i>	Virtual Network System	<p>Figure 1 version:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 18 • Numerical: 1 <p>Full version:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boolean: 40 • Numerical: 3 	<p>Figure 1 version:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 1 • Arithmetic: 1 <p>Full version:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logic: 63 • Arithmetic: 4 	<p>Figure 1 version:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 63 • Measured: 315 <p>Full version:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total SAT: 2,130,000 • Measured: 10,650,000 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feature level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (1) Dependency $\in [L, M, H]$: Function: Maximum (2) Usability $\in (1, 10)$: Function: Mean (3) Security $\in [L, M, H]$: Function: Minimum • Configuration level: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (4) Time $\in (1,10^3)$ seconds (5) Energy $\in (1,10^3)$ joules

Figure 20. VNFs in the Edge-related systems deeply analyzed with our CQL framework.

3.3.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The following tables contain SAVRUS, the AVA and NDF modules, and the CQL framework, decomposed into the different components of the MAPE-K.

Table 23. Energy-aware edge resource management.

N-MAPE-K Component	Smart Analyser of Variability Requirements in Unknown Spaces (SAVRUS)
Sensors + Monitor	If available, the system receives updated information on the network, its resources, and energy rate measurements.
Analyze	Inputs are pre-processed to foresee the specific infrastructure components required by the VNF and the alternatives to the current infrastructure.
Plan	SAVRUS uncovers the main noteworthy components and interacting components affecting energy consumption, latency, or other quality attributes.
Execution + Effector	Considering the information returned by SAVRUS, the list is ordered by the strength of the effect and colored green for a decrease and red for an increase.
Knowledge	Fused variability and quality model of the application, the hardware and software configuration of the infrastructure (either full or partial), the quality measurements, if available, and developer constraints.
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	By reinforcement learning, each execution updates the components and interaction weights to increase the efficiency and accuracy of future iterations. The weights are null by default, but a series of guided executions could be considered as a pre-training set. For energy consumption or latency, the training loss is to maximize the weights (most affecting components and interactions). The states are statistically chosen, the actions are to increment or decrement, and the reward is to apply the outcome to the weights.
N-MAPE-K Component	Application Variability Adapter (AVA)
Sensors + Monitor	The system receives updated information on the status of the nodes (available resources and availability).

Analyze	Inputs are processed to foresee the specific infrastructure components required by the VNF and the capabilities of the current infrastructure.
Plan	The AVA maximizes the number of supported features and upper range of the attributes (of the VNF received as an input) while minimizing their lower range and maximizing the number of supported features.
Execution + Effector	Considering the information returned by the AVA module, the infrastructure administrator orders the deployment of the VNF in the infrastructure (if supported) or configures a new VNF with the requirements highlighted by the AVA.
Knowledge	Feature model of the application, the hardware and software configuration of the infrastructure (either full or partial), and the infrastructure's status.
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	This module uses predefined information about the resources that each VNF configuration needs to operate to ensure a certain quality of service. As the number of deployments increases and since the infrastructure is monitored at all times, it is possible to check whether the estimates are met and how they can be met in case they are not (e.g., by allocating more resources). Therefore, the system is able to provide increasingly more precise solutions tailored to the infrastructure/VNFs.
N-MAPE-K Component	New Devices Finder (NDF)
Sensors + Monitor	The system receives updated information on the status of the nodes (available resources and availability).
Analyze	Inputs are processed to foresee the specific infrastructure's components and QoS required by the VNF and the alternative configurations of the infrastructure.
Plan	The NDF detects all VNF's requisites non-supported by the current infrastructure configuration and returns a minimal configuration (i.e., the minimal set of features and minimal value of the attributes) of the minimal set of infrastructure nodes to be acquired and added to the given infrastructure to run the VNFs properly.
Execution + Effector	Considering the information returned by this module, the infrastructure administrator acquires the new devices needed to support the desired VNF (if any) before deploying it.
Knowledge	Full configuration (software and hardware) of the nodes presented in the infrastructure, a configured VNF, and infrastructure's status.
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	The NDF module uses information about VNF requirements (e.g., CPU cycles, bandwidth, memory) to estimate the resources needed to achieve a certain QoS. In this way, the amount of resources (i.e., nodes) to be included in the infrastructure is calculated. As time goes by, it is possible to obtain more accurate information about VNFs requirements by comparing the current QoS with the expected, providing more and more accurate solutions over time.
N-MAPE-K Component	Categorical Query Language (CQL) framework
Sensors + Monitor	The system receives updated information on the network, resources, energy rate measurements, if available, and QoS requirements. Additionally, SAVRUS results help to filter the data for the noteworthy ones.
Analyze	Inputs are pre-processed to foresee the specific infrastructure components required by the VNF and the capabilities of the current infrastructure.
Plan	CQL framework decomposes the QoS requirements into a sequence of simpler queries to execute.
Execution + Effector	The CQL framework runs the sequence and provides the specific results in the format indicated (e.g., a list of components reflecting the most efficient alternative).
Knowledge	Fused variability and quality model of the application, the hardware and software configuration of the infrastructure (either full or partial), the

	quality measurements if available, the developer constraints, the reasoning query, the results format, and the external QoS requirements.
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	By functors composition, simple queries are cached and re-used several times with complex goals like guided sampling or weighted optimization. Nevertheless, specific training functions and learning algorithms are not yet implemented.

3.3.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The three modules described in the previous subsections are aligned with the 5G functionalities used in 5GPPP vertical trials. These modules allow improving energy efficiency inside network slices by making smart network management that guarantees the QoS. Instead of focusing only on the network energy efficiency, such as ITU-R M.2410-0, which mainly promotes an efficient data transmission in a loaded case and reduces the energy consumption when there is no data, the works presented here focus on energy efficiency in NFV and VNF energy consumption reduction [25].

The main contribution of these works is to provide tools that help to understand which mobile network features at the application layer are causing a waste of energy in Edge computing environments. This is not explicitly addressed in current energy efficient studies of mobile networks and other 5G-PPP projects, assuming that the main cause of energy leaks is produced during idle times, when no data is being transmitted but equipments are still on. Other features, like the type of virtualization used to instantiate VNFs inside base stations, may influence the final energy footprint.

3.4 Data-driven resource orchestration

In this section, we present the latest status of our work on data-driven resource orchestration. In D3.1, Section 5.4 describes the problem we aim to solve. As operators now deploy 5G SA networks, one of the main challenges they face is managing the heterogeneity of devices and their service demand. This is particularly dire when considering that the key promise of 5G is to enable use cases for URLLC and mMTC, which did not anticipate the success of the global operational model that IoT verticals chose (i.e., the ability to deploy their devices in different economies across the world with minimal management overhead by overloading the international mobility function of the cellular ecosystem). Our results show that, as operators prepare to deploy 5G SA solutions, there is a need to accommodate a fine-granular approach in responding to the demand coming from devices deployed globally.

3.4.1 Requirements in D2.2

Table 24. Requirements satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-MTERM-000	Our approach aims to leverage the 5G CUPS to explore the best location of the UPF for specific groups of devices that rely on the core network of the network we analyze but rent different radio resources across the world.
FR-MTERM-004	Our solution builds into the big data platform of a real-world operator to generate different analytics and device-level features, which we then use to cluster the devices based on their network requirements. We run this analysis as multiple time-scales (1h interval, 4h interval, 24h interval).
FR-MTERM-021	Our solution provides the resulting clusters of devices to the Network Intelligence Orchestrator, which can then run the per-device classification and allocate resources to the different devices.

3.4.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The solution for data-driven resource orchestration is aligned with the guideline on Self-learning models based on dataflow programming. More specifically, the data collection mechanisms we integrate within the operator big data cluster include decentralized and distributed data management pipelines that deal with the data collected from heterogeneous devices (e.g., devices representing the three different pillars for 5G networks: connected cars as a use case of URLLC, smart meters as a representative of mMTC, and smartphones for eMBB).

3.4.3 Solution

To inform the design of our solution, we investigate the diversity within the device population that connects to the network of an operational MNO in the UK (namely Virgin Media O2 UK). First, we explore the adoption of 5G-capable smartphones in the UK. Then, we analyze three representative groups of devices: connected cars as a use case of URLLC, smart meters as a representative of mMTC, and

smartphones for eMBB. We analyze their spatial and temporal behaviors by computing daily metrics and exploring their evolution (e.g., over the last two years, in 2022 vs. 2020).

Our analysis found that some specific metrics that we consider capture the fundamentally different behaviors of the three groups of devices that correspond to the main 5G use-cases. This validates that the 5G design correctly predicted the importance of their corresponding use case areas. However, when building the devices samples, we found that the global deployment model IoT verticals prefer is quickly becoming the norm (i.e., less than 2% of connected cars in our sample are native to the operator we analyze), reducing the visibility for the radio network operator into end-user requirements. Despite this, we observe similarities in the network behavior of devices in different categories (e.g., between smartphones and connected cars). Furthermore, within each group of devices, different traffic patterns emerge, which point to the need for the network operators to apply tailored approaches in order to cater to the requirements of those devices. This requires a fine-granular understanding of the devices' demand and intelligent analytics solutions within the operator environment to match devices to their predicted requirements profiles. In this section, we take the first step in this direction and investigate the emerging patterns for these three major 5G device categories, both in terms of similarity between device categories and also the heterogeneity within a standalone use case belonging to one category.

3.4.3.1 Inter-category similarities

We take a random sample of 1 million devices (approximately 330,000 devices per use-case category) during a typical working week and apply an explanatory clustering method to study the similarities between device categories. For this, we dissect the behavior of devices, ignoring their device category (i.e., smartphone, connected car, smart meter). To do so, we generate and further process a set of 456 weekly metrics that capture traffic statistics, mobility, signaling, handovers, and time spent on the network as input features. We discard RAT-based metrics (e.g., the number of Attach events in 3G) since if all the devices are 5G-capable in the future, these sliced metrics will be less meaningful.

We generate this large set of features by processing data feeds we collect from the UK MNO in real time. We implemented several jobs that feed from the dataset we previously explained in Section 5.4 of D3.1. We give in Figure 21 an overview of the data processing logic we have in place, as we integrated it in the big data cluster together with the operator. We will report on the data processing pipeline integration in the operator's infrastructure in D5.2.

Figure 21. Airflow DAG for the data processing pipeline that generates the per-device features that we collect and further use for device classification.

We leverage a simple feed-forward neural network autoencoder to reduce the dimensions of the feature set to 8. We use a three-layer Encoder-Decoder architecture with 128, 64, and 32 hidden units and consider mean-squared-error (MSE) as the loss function. We run experiments for 50 epochs, where the batch size and learning rate are set to 128 and 0.001, respectively.

Table 25. Clustering results on a sub-sample of devices.

Clustering approach	Silhouette	Davies-Bouldin	Sample Size [%]
K-means	0.54	0.6	38, 33, 29
Gaussian Mixture	0.53	0.59	36, 32, 30

Birch	0.57	0.45	62, 34, 2
Spectral	0.28	0.85	42, 36, 22
Agglomerative Clustering	0.53	0.58	45, 40, 15

Then, we serve the autoencoder output as features for the clustering algorithms. To test the optimal number of clusters and the clustering approach, we first take a smaller random sample of 60,000 users. We choose the number of clusters equal to three based on the elbow-method on the within-cluster sum of squared distances to the center. We compare the result of different algorithms using the Python Scikit-learn library in Table 25, considering two scores. The model with the highest Silhouette score or the lowest Davies-Bouldin score point to the best approach. Although the clustering algorithms result in a different group of users, as shown in the last column of Table 25, we observe that they entirely fail to separate the three groups of devices; this hints at potential similarity among device categories that gathers them into the same cluster. Notice we exclude the results of the share of device categories in clusters due to insufficient space. Hereafter, we use Birch clustering, which yields the best score.

To further justify the clustering approach, we use Representational Similarity Matrices (RSMs) and examine the cosine similarity between the representations of each pair of users in the same category (Figure 22.a) and in the same cluster (Figure 22.b) for a random sample of 1,000 users. Square sections in Figure 22 - left indicate the similarity between connected cars and smartphones. The square sections of the RSM lying along the blue diagonal in Figure 22.b correspond to the similarities between users in the same cluster, implying that the clustering approach can capture the similarities among users with the same behavior.

Figure 22. RSMs between pairs of users in a random sample of 1000 end-users.

Ultimately, we apply clustering on the whole 1 million users and show the results in Figure 23. As it appears in Figure 23.a, clusters contain 57%, 38%, and 5% of users. Then, we focus on finding the essential features enabling us to differentiate clusters. Figure 23.b shows the relative difference between the median of clusters and the overall median for the top ten features. The clusters and their relative deviations from the median value are depicted as lines in this radar plot. Overall, we catch three kinds of behavior: most users are in cluster 0 in the middle with a median of 0.5MB DL traffic, connecting to 14 sectors per day (shown as a blue line in Figure 23.b). Whereas a limited number of users in cluster 2 are highly mobile and generate 1.8x higher DL traffic and transmit 2.2x more between radio layers on the network than cluster 0 comparing their medians. The last group of users in cluster 1 is stationary devices, mainly smart meters, that do not generate much DL traffic and remain in the same place. Overall, the results not only confirm the similarity between device categories (Figure 22.a) but also contribute to the smart user classification.

3.4.3.2 Intra-use-case category variation

We separate connected cars sending the top-ranked APN (i.e., covering the most significant share of 44% among cars) on a typical working day. Then, we input them into the k-means clustering by considering only traffic behavior (i.e., DL/UL traffic and signaling messages) and mobility behavior (i.e., number of radio sectors used, gyration) as input features. We choose 4 clusters based on the elbow method evaluating the within-cluster sum of squares. Table 26 shows the characteristic of each cluster based on the delta variation percentage of each metric from the corresponding median of smartphones. 75% of these cars are in cluster 0 with limited mobility and low traffic, whereas traffic of 1.2% in cluster 2 is higher than the median of smartphones. (i.e., 1st vs. 3rd row in Table 24). The median gyration of cars in cluster 1 is 18 times higher than that of the smartphone, while it is only 3.3 times higher for cluster 3. This confirms our hypothesis that neither the device category nor the APN is a reliable approach to group devices with consistent behavior and similar traffic patterns. Currently, transparency into device requirements is provided by the APN, IMSI ranges (full or partial), and, in some cases, the specific RAT. While it is critical to identify different services/devices for efficient 5G network slicing, we conclude that

the APN approach is sub-optimal, as devices using the same APN behaved in different ways and generated divergent traffic patterns. This highlights the importance of smart user classification in the context of IoT market growth to be able to benefit from and exploit better 5G innovations.

Figure 23. The results of clustering users (a) Devices breakdown with respect to the clusters. (b) The relative difference of the top 10 features per cluster to the overall median per feature; we normalize it by standard scaler to fit all features between [-1, 1].

Table 26. Cars clusters withing the same group using a top APN. We show the percentage of the cluster in the sample (in column ‘%’) and the deviation of the main features per cluster from the median values for smartphones.

Cluster #	%	DL	UL/DL ratio	Gyration	Characteristics
0	75.2	-99.48	91.98	-22.98	Low mobility Low traffic volume
1	5.1	-92.7	56,2	1,703.14	High mobility Significant traffic volume
2	1.2	853.4	-93.2	1.47	Low mobility High traffic volume
3	18.4	-96.5	55.02	235,6	High mobility High traffic volume

3.4.3.3 Network Function Placement – proof of concept

Given a smart classification of the device population connecting to an operator, we investigate the potential of using third-party infrastructure in order to host core network functions for an operator deploying their device globally (e.g., offering managed connectivity for connected cars worldwide). The split of the user plane from the control plane at both the radio front and the core is one of the major upgrades in 5G. This paves the way not just for better management of data and control packets but also to enable truly global operations of an operator. We argue that, with this approach, any mobile operator can potentially convert into a global provider [26], avoiding home-routed roaming configuration and enabling the end-user to achieve a good experience potentially worldwide through regional breakout. We envision a scenario where the mobile operator provides the local breakout solution to each end-user, in correlation to its corresponding requirements, as we extracted them from the clustering analysis above. We will further report on our pilot implementation in D5.2.

3.4.4 N-MAPE-K representation

Table 27. Requirements satisfaction.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors + Monitor	Sensing and monitoring are collecting the raw data feeds from the mobile network infrastructure, as we explained in D5.1.

Analyze	We generate a large set of per-device features to capture the behavior and network activity of the devices connecting to the radio network of Virgin Media O2 UK. We integrated this processing pipeline within the big data platform the operator deploys. From these, we then selected only a small subset of 8 features to run the clustering of the device population,
Plan	Based on the engineered features, we run unsupervised clustering to extract the prevalent traffic patterns within the device population of the operator, specifically highlighting the challenges in dealing with inbound roaming devices.
Execute + Effector	Based on the output of the clustering module, the network operator can make informed decisions on the optimal placement of network functions.
Knowledge	The clustering module gives insight into the heterogeneity of the device population, even within the same vertical (e.g., connected cars). This then serves as input for optimizing cloud-based core network deployment.

3.4.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The solution we propose is based on the virtualization of network resources and the split of the user plane from the control plane (CUPS, introduced in 3GPP Release 14) at the core. Thus, it is aligned with ETSI NFV and 3GPP standards.

3.5 Multi-timescale network slice reservation

Network slicing optimization is of high importance given the current softwarization trend of wireless networks coupled with the emerging complex interaction between over-the-top service providers (SPs) and network operators' infrastructure (NOs). This section introduces our contribution to studying the problem of deciding, online and at two different time scales, the optimal amount of network resources' slices from the perspective of SPs.

3.5.1 Requirements in D2.2

The solution described in the following subsections fulfills the following requirements proposed in D2.2.

Table 28. Multi-timescale network slice reservation. Requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-MTERM-000	The proposed algorithm is indeed automated and performs provably optimal lower-time scale reservations given the higher time scale ones. In fact, slice reservation and customization are done online each 1 - 24 hours (depending on the granularity of the model). Furthermore, refinement of the reserved slice (in terms of size and content) is done at a scale of 1 – 60 minutes.
FR-MTERM-020	The coordination between the two time scales is available since lower performance (and high expenses) due to short-sighted slice reservations will affect the reward for the larger time scale. Hence, at the following iteration, more resources will be booked well ahead of time. Similarly, in the situation of extra available resources, less will be reserved at the next higher time-scale iteration. This coordination is a result of the reward for the long-term reservation actions being dependent not only on how well it will meet the demand but also on how many times it needs to be modified (i.e., revised and appended).

3.5.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The proposed algorithm adheres to the design guideline of "Adapting a known reward function to networking". Namely, following the standard practice, we use a concave utility function to model the benefit of the service provider from using a certain amount of network resources. We explored the well-known family of alpha-fair utility functions and chose the log utility. Such a reward (i.e., objective) function has the characteristic of "diminishing return", which arises naturally in economic slice reservation systems.

3.5.3 Solution

The solution was fully described in Deliverable 2.2, Sec. 5.5.

3.5.4 N-MAPE-K representation

Next, we show how the different components of the proposed solution can be mapped to an N-MAPE-K structure.

Table 29. N-MAPE-K mapping for the proposed solution.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors	Sensing is merely observing the user demands for the resources in a network slice via appropriately designed network traffic analysis APIs.
Monitor	-
Analyze	-
Plan:	Planning is represented by the primal-dual gradient steps performed by the algorithm. Namely, we take a gradient step in the allocation decision variables space towards maximizing the reward, and a gradient step, in the dual penalty variables, towards minimizing budget constraint violation (See Fig. 41, in D2.2).
Execute	-
Effector	The effector can be an (automated) network virtual resource manager software.

3.5.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The proposed solution is based on the virtualization of network resources. Thus, it is aligned with ETSI NFV where the proposed-slice reservation algorithm can act as a resource allocation manager for the virtualized resources.

4 Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) control

This section presents a NI Functionality designed to optimize the operation of a RIS-aided Radio Access Network, a problem that was introduced in D3.1 [1].

4.1 Requirements

The mapping between the requirements established for RIS control in D2.2 [2] is presented in Table 30.

Table 30. RIS control, requirement satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-RIS-000	This NI Functionality jointly optimizes the precoding configuration of a base station in conventional Radio Access Networks and the passive beamforming parameters of a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS)
FR-RIS-001	This NI Functionality jointly optimizes the precoding configuration of a base station in conventional Radio Access Networks and the passive beamforming parameters of a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS)
FR-RIS-002	This NI Functionality uses Channel State Information (CSI) in a BS to do the optimization.
FR-RIS-003	This requirement is not yet met.
FR-RIS-004	This requirement is not yet met.
NFR-RIS-000	This NI Functionality optimizes the configuration of a RIS to maximize the sum rate performance of a RAN. The validation of this requirement will be presented in D5.2.
NFR-RIS-001	This requirement is not yet met.
NFR-RIS-002	This requirement is not yet met.
NFR-RIS-003	This NI Functionality optimizes the configuration of a RIS, assuming no power gain in the RIS

4.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The development of this solution has followed the guidelines established in D2.2 [2], Section 4.1.6, to build on classical optimization models, when possible, to expedite decision-making. More specifically, the solution presented in this section recasts a non-convex formulation into a problem that can be solved with classical semidefinite relaxation techniques, which renders a solver that can be executed in sub-millisecond timescales without requiring fitting data.

4.3 Solution

In D3.1[1], Section 6, we described a problem that aimed at optimizing jointly the precoding strategy of a Base Station (BS) and the passive beamforming configuration of a RIS to minimize the sum mean squared error, which is known to relate to the sum rate performance.

We refer the reader to D3.1 [1] for the description of the notation used in this section. Formally, as described therein, our problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \underset{\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{W}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_k \sum_j |\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_j|^2 - 2 \sum_k \text{Re}\{\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \mathbf{w}_k\} \\
 & \text{subject to} && |v_i|^2 \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \\
 & && v_{N+1} = 1; \\
 & && \|\mathbf{W}\|_F^2 \leq P;
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 1. RIS problem formulation.

where \mathbf{W} is the transmitter's precoding configuration, and \mathbf{v} is the RIS configuration; $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_k \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_k^H) \mathbf{G} \\ \mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{N+1 \times M}$, with \mathbf{h}_k^H being the Hermitian transpose of the channel between the RIS and user k , and $\mathbf{h}_{d,k}^H$ being the channel between the BS and user k , and P is the power budget of the BS.

In this document, we focus on solving the aforementioned problem for one single UE, hence we can drop the subindex k . We will solve this problem for multiple users in D3.3.

In order to separately exploit the convexity in \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{W} of our objective function in **Equation 1**, we let the RIS parameters in \mathbf{v} be fixed such that we can first focus on finding the precoding strategy \mathbf{W} . Since perfect Channel State Information (CSI) is available at the BS, when \mathbf{v} is fixed the optimal linear transmit precoding vector is known to be the one matched to the (here, effective) channel between the BS and the UE, maximizing the received SNR, which is given by maximum-ratio transmission (MRT), i.e.,

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{MRT}} = \sqrt{P} \frac{\mathbf{G}^H \Phi^H \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{h}_d}{\|\mathbf{G}^H \Phi^H \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{h}_d\|}.$$

Thus, once the precoding strategy is obtained, the problem reduces to the optimization of the RIS setting parameters in Φ . Consider the received MSE after MRT precoding

$$\text{MSE}_{\text{MRT}} = \mathbb{E}[|y - s|^2],$$

where the expectation is over the symbol s and the noise n , which are assumed independent. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MSE}_{\text{MRT}} &= \mathbb{E}[|(\mathbf{h}^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_d^H) \mathbf{w}_{\text{MRT}} - 1|s + n|^2] \\ &= P \|\mathbf{h}^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_d^H\|^2 - 2\sqrt{P} \|\mathbf{h}^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_d^H\| + 1 + \sigma_n^2. \end{aligned}$$

We thus formulate the following optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} &\underset{\Phi}{\text{minimize}} && \|\mathbf{h}^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_d^H\|^2 - 2\frac{\sqrt{P}}{P} \|\mathbf{h}^H \Phi \mathbf{G} + \mathbf{h}_d^H\| \\ &\text{subject to} && |[\Phi]_{ii}|^2 \leq 1 \quad \forall i \\ &&& [\Phi]_{ij} = 0 \quad \forall i \neq j. \end{aligned}$$

Equation 2. RIS problem. Single user.

We recast the latter into the following optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} &\underset{\mathbf{v}}{\text{minimize}} && \|\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}\|^2 - 2\frac{\sqrt{P}}{P} \|\mathbf{v}^H \bar{\mathbf{H}}\| \\ &\text{subject to} && |v_i|^2 \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \\ &&& v_{N+1} = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Equation 3. RIS Problem Single User, P2.

Note that Problem P2 is non-convex in \mathbf{v} but it can be solved efficiently by standard convex-concave programming as it is a summation of a convex function, i.e., the squared norm term, minus a second convex function, i.e., the norm term.

An alternative yet simpler approach defines $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{v}\mathbf{v}^H$ and solve the following optimization problem

$$\begin{aligned} &\underset{\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{V} \succeq \mathbf{0}}{\text{minimize}} && \text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{H}}\bar{\mathbf{H}}^H \mathbf{V}) - 2\frac{\sqrt{P}}{P} \sqrt{\text{tr}(\bar{\mathbf{H}}\bar{\mathbf{H}}^H \mathbf{V})} \\ &\text{subject to} && [\mathbf{V}]_{ii} \leq 1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N; \\ &&& [\mathbf{V}]_{N+1, N+1} = 1, v_{N+1} = 1; \\ &&& \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V} & \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{v}^H & 1 \end{bmatrix} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \\ &&& \text{rank}(\mathbf{V}) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

Equation 4. RIS problem. Single User. P3.

Note that Problem P3 is non-convex in \mathbf{V} due to the rank constraint. However, by employing semidefinite relaxation, the latter can be turned into a convex problem by relaxing the rank constraint. The resulting problem can then be solved via standard semidefinite programming as, e.g., CVX. An approximate

solution to Problem P3 can be obtained from the relaxed convex problem via Gaussian randomization. While the optimality of Gaussian Randomization is only proven for a small, well-defined family of optimization problems, it guarantees an $\frac{\pi}{4}$ -approximation of the optimal objective value of the original problem for a sufficiently large number of randomizations.

Lastly, note that the RIS parameters $\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^N$ can be obtained by setting

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i &= |v_i|, \quad \text{and} \\ \phi_i &= \arg(v_i^*), \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \end{aligned}$$

In practical systems, it is difficult to control exactly the state of each reflecting element as this control is implemented through sensible variations of the equivalent impedance of each reflecting cell. It is thus not practical to allow any possible state for the absorption coefficients $\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and phase reflection $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^N$ of the i -th reflecting element. In this respect, we propose an extension of the method before, dubbed as Lo-RISMA, which decouples the optimization of $\{\alpha_i\}_{i=1}^N$ and $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^N$ to include practical implementation constraints, namely, each reflecting element is activated in a binary fashion and each phase shift can vary on a given set of discrete values.

We start by treating the binary activation assumption. Namely, each reflecting element can have only one of two states, i.e., $\alpha_i \in \{0,1\} \forall i$.

In the considered single-UE scenario, the maximization of the sum rate is equivalent to the minimization of the received MSE or maximization of the received SNR. Let us define the effective channel as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}^H) \bar{\Phi} \mathbf{G} \\ \mathbf{h}_d^H \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{N+1 \times M},$$

with $\bar{\Phi} \triangleq \text{diag}[e^{j\phi_1}, \dots, e^{j\phi_N}]$ and the binary vector $\mathbf{b} \in \{0,1\}^{N+1}$, where each b_i indicates whether the corresponding reflecting element is active or not. Hence, we have that $\alpha_i = b_i \ i = 1, \dots, N$ and $\Phi = \text{diag}(b_1 e^{j\phi_1}, \dots, b_N e^{j\phi_N})$. The received SNR after MRT precoding is given by

$$\text{SNR}_{\text{MRT}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{b}^T \tilde{\mathbf{H}}\|^2}{\sigma_n^2},$$

Which is clearly maximized when $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{1}$.

Consider now the case where the phases $\{\phi_i\}_{i=1}^N$ are quantized with a given number of bits. The ideal feasible set $[0, 2\pi)$ is thus quantized into 2^b uniformly spaced discrete points as

$$\phi_i \in \mathcal{Q} \triangleq \left\{ \frac{2\pi}{2^b} m \right\}_{m=0}^{2^b-1} \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad i = 1, \dots, N.$$

To achieve such quantization, we simply project the phase shifts obtained by solving Problem P2 or P3 onto the closest point within the constellation in \mathcal{Q} .

An evaluation of this approach will be presented in D5.2.

4.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The algorithm presented above is not a data-driven or machine learning approach. Instead, it relies on mathematical models and convex optimization approaches. This implies that neither a data pre-processing phase nor the definition of a reward function (used for learning in reinforcement learning) is needed here.

The following table describes this functionality using the N-MAKE-K framework proposed in D2.2 for integration into the global DAEMON's framework.

Table 31. Requirements satisfaction.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors + Monitor	Channel estimation between one UE and the base station and channel estimation between the UE and the RIS
Analyze	N/A
Plan	Application of semidefinite programming with, e.g., CVX (a standard solver)
Execution + Effector	Enforcement of the precoding configuration in the base station and phase shifts in the RIS
Knowledge	Wireless link's sum mean squared error (SMSE)
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	N/A (convex model)

4.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

SDOs have not yet provided specifications for the integration of RIS and 3GPP mobile networks. Recently, ETSI has created a new specification group (ISG) where DAEMON plans to contribute actively. Though, at the moment, there is no standard architectural specification that supports RISs. Figure 24 depicts an architecture that has been proposed in [19] and integrates RIS control and management into O-RAN's ecosystem. This view aligns very well with that of DAEMON project.

Figure 24. Proposed architecture to integrate O-RAN and RIS (reproduced from [19]).

As you can see from the figure, Reconfigurable, Intelligent, and Sustainable wireless Environment (RISE) controllers can be operated from O-RAN's SMO via appropriate plug-ins. Guided through ML models, convex models or other models, RISE controllers are hence in charge of controlling spatially distributed RISs within the B5G network components. RISE controllers are connected to the orchestrator via a new reference point (Rx) that instructs transmitter configurations on long timescales (e.g., minutes) for specific environments or given use cases. In parallel, the RISE controller can adjust the RIS parameters based on the received feedback as well as the desired KPIs.

As this NIF demonstrated, tight coordination between base stations and RISs is important. Hence, this architecture proposes a new interface (R2) to create a direct link between the near-real-time (near-RT) RAN intelligent controller (RIC) and the RISE controller. This will allow simultaneously controlling the configurations of RISs and the beamforming of BSs in very short timescales. Finally, an "Open Environment" interface can be developed between the RIS elements and the radio units handling the digital front to bring flexibility and programmability.

5 In-backhaul learning

5.1 Flow-level Random Forest models in programmable switches

As described in Section 7 of D3.1 [3], we tackle the challenge of meeting a sub-millisecond latency for beyond 5G services, by bringing intelligence at the Transport level of the (so-called) edge to core continuum. Specifically, we implement the inference phase of supervised classification in programmable switches in order to perform traffic classification. In Section 4.5.1 of D5.1 [3], we presented an early analysis of solutions in the literature that address the same problem, concluding that Random Forest (RF) models are a promising candidate for early flow classification into the user plane.

In this section, we present Flowrest, a solution integrating large RF models in off-the-shelf programmable switches to perform inference on individual traffic flows at line rate.

5.1.1 Requirements in D2.2

Table 32. Flow-level Random Forest models in programmable switches. Requirements satisfaction.

Requirement from D2.2 [2]	Rationale
FR-IBSSI-000	The solutions shall learn network policies using the user plane itself. We perform traffic classification at line rate, paving the way to learn specific network policies for specific classes of traffic.
FR-IBSSI-001	The solution shall provide intelligence as a service to vertical 3 rd parties. Our solution encompasses interaction with the control plane where classification results can be potentially exploited by other services.
FR-IBSSI-002	The solution shall integrate NI within programmable switches. Our solution performs inference fully in Tofino switches.
NFR-IBSSI-000	The model should be encoded ad-hoc to the switch architecture. Our solution map RF models into the programmable ASIC of the switch. Besides, it considers multiple adaptations to the switch's hardware constraints by design.
NFR-IBSSI-001	The model design should be resource prudent. In our solution, we employ models whose hyperparameters are selected with the best tradeoff between performance and resource usage.

5.1.2 Guidelines from D2.2

As reported in D2.2 [2], we advocate adopting Random Forest models to perform inference in programmable user planes at line rate. The rationale behind this choice is that other approaches, like those based on deep learning, do not provide any significant advantage for the user plane use cases analyzed. Random Forests show a classification performance similar to or superior to deep learning models in such tasks. Furthermore, implementing deep learning models in resource-constrained hardware is a much more significant challenge, resulting in a dramatic limitation of the complexity of such models.

5.1.3 Solution

In-switch tree-based inference has been investigated in multiple works [27][28]. Such solutions take advantage of the PISA architecture programmable Parser to extract data from the packet headers, as described in D3.1 [1]. The data extracted are then used as features that feed tree-based models encoded into the match and action tables of the architecture.

The main design dichotomy in these works is between packet versus flow level classification. At the packet level, the classification is performed for each and every packet that traverses the switch. At the flow level, instead, the classification considers the data gathered from the first n packets of the flow and is performed just once when the n th packet of the flow traverses the switch.

For these reasons, packet-level models are simpler to implement as they can use as features the data extracted from the headers of each packet effortlessly.

On the contrary, flow-level models rely on features that are calculated with the data extracted from n packets. Indeed, flow-level models need a dedicated logic to calculate, store and update features that consider multiple packets for each flow. Nevertheless, flow-level solutions have a two-folded advantage as i) flow-level features have proved to be of paramount importance in traffic classification [29][30] and ii) the classification model does not have to be run for every packet but just once for each flow. Building on such considerations, we designed a practical framework for user-plane per-flow RF inference.

Figure 25. Overview of the full system proposed.

Figure 25 shows the entire system where Flowrest sits. We assume that not all the traffic traversing the switch is targeted by inference. As an example, we may be interested in performing the inference to inspect just a specific range of IP addresses suspected of carrying malicious traffic. The portion of traffic that is outside such a scope can be forwarded normally. The targeted traffic, instead, has to go through flow management and inference blocks. The system encompasses all the components needed to i) perform inference in the switch, ii) manage the flows and iii) perform normal forwarding. It also shows the interaction with the Controller to periodically update the information on the classified flows. Such a mechanism is important to allow the Controller to integrate the classified flows with the normal forwarding logic. As an example, a target flow that has been classified as non-malicious can be forwarded normally. It is also important to release the switch resources that are allocated for its tracking.

The blocks in dark blue color are applied to every packet traversing the switch. They are responsible for parsing the packet headers², pre-processing such data in order to identify the portion of traffic targeted by the inference, and forwarding the traffic non-targeted by the inference or already classified. The traffic targeted by the inference goes through the Match Action Units (MAUs) that are dedicated to flow classification. For each flow identified by the switch, the inference is applied after a specific number n of packets. Early forwarding is applied to packets before the n^{th} . The n^{th} packet goes through the model and it is re-circulated to update the switch registers with the class information. After the classification decision is taken, all the packets of a flow can be forwarded accordingly. Periodically, the switch informs the controller of the flows that have been classified with a digest. The controller can, in turn, update the forwarding logic.

Section 5.1.3.1 describes how we manage the flows inside the switch. Section 5.1.3.2 presents the mapping strategy to encode RF models into the switch architecture. Finally, section 5.1.3.3 details the switch-tailored feature engineering and hyper-parameters tuning.

5.1.3.1 Flow management

The management of the flows is enabled by storing and updating flow information into Static Random Access Memory (SRAM) switch registers. The information stored concerns the flow identifier, the stateful features and the class information (when available). The flow identifier is calculated by CRC32 hashing a 5-tuple with source and destination ports and addresses and the protocol used. A CRC16 hash of the 5-tuple is calculated and used as a unique register index to access the flow information, stored across multiple SRAMs. When a packet arrives, both hashes are calculated and the register index is used to access the SRAMs. If the slots are empty, the information of the flow is stored. If the slots are not empty, we check if the flow identifier stored is correct and, if that is the case, the stateful features are updated. If the identifier is not correct, a hash collision occurs and the flow cannot be tracked. The collision rate is greatly reduced³ by the periodic update of the forwarding logic and the consequent removal of the classified flows from the registers. In the case of feature updates, from a technical standpoint, the read and update operations must be done at the same time. This is allowed by using a RegisterAction extern of the Tofino Native Architecture (TNA) that exploits Stateful Arithmetic Logic Units (S-ALUs).

² After the parsing, the packet data are carried through the pipeline via the Packet Header Vector (PHV).

³ Nearly 0% in the use cases tested.

5.1.3.2 *RF models mapping*

We reproduced and integrated⁴ with the presented framework a custom version of the mapping proposed in Planter [31], as we consider it as the state-of-the-art strategy to ensure scalable multi-tree support. The key element of such a strategy is that one dedicated table is used for each model feature, even if the feature occurs many times and in multiple forest trees. This approach guarantees that each feature is processed in exactly one MAU. The nodes of the trees where a feature occurs are then encoded as range matches in such a table.

Figure 26. RF mapping into MAUs example.

The toy example in Figure 26 explains this process for one tree. Two features are in play, A and B. Feature A=5 matches with the second row of the corresponding table and the action returns two codes, 1 and 0, as the feature occurs two times in the tree. Feature B=6 matches with the second row of its table and the corresponding action return 1. The resulting *codeword=101* is then used to match against a final table (in orange in the figure), which matches with the third row and returns *Class=3*. The example can be easily generalized for multiple trees. The nodes of the additional trees would generate additional columns in the feature tables (in blue color) and one additional table for each tree. The final class of the RF is selected with a voting system that selects the class with the votes. In case of a tie, the system considers the certainty levels of the leaves involved to select the final class.

5.1.3.3 *Switch-tailored model design*

An important aspect of Flowerest is that we consider the hardware constraints of the device at the ML model design phase. We apply strategies to ensure that the RF that are trained are compatible with the architecture of the programmable switch by design. Such strategies concern i) the adaptation of the representation of the features to the hardware specifications and ii) the tailoring of the choice of hyperparameters in the RFs to the underlying hardware.

As already mentioned, to encode each tree node into tables, we use a range match bounded to a maximum number of bits⁵. This limit affects flow-level (stateful) features, particularly time-related ones represented with floating point precision. We adapt the feature size without losing performance.

As shown in Figure 26, we use wildcards to represent the codewords that map the tree leaves. This operation is technically a non-exact match, which can be performed with a maximum number of bits. To respect such a constraint, we limit the size of each tree.

5.1.4 *MAPE-K representation*

Next, we show how this NI-assisted functionality can be mapped to an N-MAPE-K structure.

Table 33. Flow-level Random Forest models in programmable switches.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors + Monitor	Data extracted from packet headers that are used as: i) identifiers of a flow; ii) features of the model.
Analyze	Stateful features of the model need to be updated on a per-flow basis, e.g., calculating averages or selecting maximum/minimum values.
Plan	Application of a Random Forest model to classify flows of packets
Execution + Effector	Update of a packet header with the class of the packet
Knowledge	Classification of flows of packets
Training Loss / State – Actions – Rewards	N/A (training is executed offline)

⁴ No code is provided by the authors of the paper.

⁵ The exact number of bits depends on the equipment and is confidential.

5.1.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

This solution is implemented by using P4⁶, which is a language to program the user plane of a variety of network devices (e.g., switches, FPGAs, NICs, etc.). The language provides a standard architecture that identifies a set of programmable blocks (e.g., parser, ingress control flow, deparser, etc.) that are common to any programmable target device supported. The vendor provides the specific hardware features of a target device as a P4 library. As our solution has been implemented on an Intel's Tofino switch, we used the Tofino Native Architecture (TNA) P4 library.

In order to run the solution in the switch, P4 code is injected from the control plane. Furthermore, the runtime behavior of the switch is also managed by the control plane. In both cases, a control API is needed. P4 community provides P4Runtime API to allow communication between a network controller and a general-purpose, P4 programmable network device. Besides, proprietary solutions exist for specific target devices. As an example, Barefoot Runtime Interface (BRI) is provided by Intel for Tofino switches.

Thanks to SDN principles, a centralized network controller can, in principle, reside at any point of the network to manage multiple programmable switches. The Open Networking Foundation (ONF) provides ONOS⁷ as the state-of-the-art SDN controller for programmable networks and SD-RAN⁸ as a software suite that is compliant with O-RAN [4] architecture.

5.2 Efficient backhaul circuit switching

We tackle the problem of backhaul circuit switching with the aim of increasing the speed and efficiency (which will be made formal later) to better support the execution of a multitude of tasks, including network intelligence-related ones. Namely, the forwarding functionality of circuit switches will be modeled and optimized so that the “bursty” traffic of data centers, which is related to ML and DL tasks, is handled more efficiently.

It is noticed that nowadays, data centers utilize both types of switches in backhaul: circuit switches as well as packet switches. Circuit switches are more suitable for tasks that require a high data rate with a low cost. They are, however, less flexible at making forwarding decisions since their configuration time is high. Specifically, the circuit switch's reconfiguration time is generally in the order of milliseconds (packet switches have such reconfiguration time in the order of microseconds). Hence, in order to harness the benefit of circuit switching, one should minimize the number of switching actions (changing the switching configuration). Such a problem is central to the network performance and has an impact on the speed of execution of a lot of in-network processes.

Mathematically, let X^* denote a doubly stochastic matrix (i.e., a scaled traffic matrix), and $\epsilon > 0$, a positive real number. Our goal is to find switching configurations (permutation matrices) P_k and the corresponding fraction of time for these configurations (weights) θ_k , such that

$$\left\| X^* - \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i P_i \right\|_F \leq \epsilon$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ is the Frobenius norm. The number of steps k after which the above term converges to ϵ is called the sparsity rate. The lower the number of steps required to achieve an ϵ -approximation, the lower the number of switching actions.

Previous works [32][33] have utilized (variants of) the classical Birkhoff method to exactly decompose X^* into the set of configurations (permutation) matrices P_k . However, little is known about the behavior or convergence properties of Birkhoff's-based algorithms, and so many fundamental questions remain still unanswered:

- How does the decomposition approximation depend on the number of switches?
- How is the Birkhoff algorithm related to other numerical methods in other fields (e.g., machine learning)?
- Is it possible to obtain an algorithm that is practical (in terms of execution times) and still delivers a good sparsity rate, enabling backhaul NI functionalities?

5.2.1 Requirements in D2.2

The solution described in the following subsections fulfills the following requirements proposed in D2.2 [2], as presented in Table 34 next.

⁶ <https://p4.org/>

⁷ <https://opennetworking.org/onos/>

⁸ <https://opennetworking.org/open-ran/>

Table 34. Efficient backhaul circuit switching, requirement satisfaction.

Functional Requirement ID	Rational
FR-IBSSI-002	The proposed solution in this subsection is not merely about data collection and pro-processing but also offloads decision-making to the data plane where the Birkhoff+ algorithm can be executed, and its decisions are implemented directly via the programmable switches.
NFR-IBSSI-001	Despite the risk of Programmable switches having limited computational capabilities and memory, the proposed algorithm was shown to be efficient (in terms of the computational task to be executed at each MAPE-K step). Recall that Birkhoff+ involves solving a single linear program at each step (as opposed to the current state-of-the-art methods, which solve many). Furthermore, a minimal number of steps is required before reaching a good approximation of the optimal switching configuration (due to the proven sparsity rate, i.e., the number of needed steps k).

5.2.2 Guidelines from D2.2

The proposed solution adheres to the guideline reported in D2.2 [2], which does not recommend the use of complex neural network models for (inference) algorithms to be executed on programmable switches at line rate. Instead, the proposed switching control algorithm is based on solving a single linear program at each step. Thus, it ensures minimal overhead and has the potential to be safely executed at line rate. Despite this non-deep learning-based control approach being conceptually and practically simple, it still provides the required performance guarantees. Namely, we are still guaranteed to converge to the optimal doubly stochastic matrix, which describes the optimal switching decisions.

5.2.3 Solution

We first study the sparsity of Birkhoff and Frank-Wolf algorithms separately before showing how they can be combined into a new algorithm we call Birkhoff+.

5.2.3.1 Characterizing Birkhoff sparsity

We are interested in characterizing the rate at which the approximation error presented earlier diminishes as a function of adding more permutation matrices. This is because we will only be executing a finite number of switching configurations. Such insight will not only provide formal performance guarantees for circuit switching operations but will also be of use for the design of new enhanced algorithms that will be provided in the following sections.

The general Birkhoff algorithm is depicted in Figure 27. The main step is marked with a black dot: finding a permutation matrix and a corresponding weight that satisfies the conditions C1-C3 (Finding these is a different task than the one we are trying to achieve here, see [34], for example. Recall that we are interested in a high sparsity rate (low number of steps to achieve ϵ -approximation)).

```

Input: Doubly stochastic matrix  $X^*$ ,  $\epsilon \geq 0$ , and  $k_{\max} \geq 1$ 
Set:  $k = 1$  and  $X_0 = \{0\}^{n \times n}$ 
while  $\|X_{k-1} - X^*\|_F > \epsilon$  and  $k \leq k_{\max}$  do
  • Compute  $P_k, \theta_k$  that satisfy Eqs. (3)-(5)
     $X_k \leftarrow X_{k-1} + \theta_k P_k$ 
     $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
end while
return  $(P_1, \dots, P_{k-1}), (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{k-1})$ 

```

Figure 27. Birkhoff general algorithm.

```

1: Input:  $X^*$  and  $X_{k-1} = \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \theta_i P_i$ 
2:  $\alpha \leftarrow (1 - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \theta_i) / n^2$ 
3:  $P_k \leftarrow \hat{P} \in \mathcal{I}_k(\alpha)$ 
4:  $\theta_k \leftarrow \text{BIRKHOFF\_STEP}(X^*, X_{k-1}, P_k)$  (Algorithm 3)

```

Figure 28. Subroutine for the black-dot-marked line in Birkhoff general algorithm.

```

1: Input:  $X^*, X_{k-1}$ , and  $P_k$ 
2: return  $\min_{a,b} \{(X^*(a,b) - X_{k-1}(a,b) - 1)P_k(a,b) + 1\}$ 

```

Figure 29. Birkhoff step.

Where the set $I_k(\alpha) := \{P \mid (X_{k-1}(a, b) + \alpha P(a, b) - 1)P_k(a, b) + 1\}$.

And conditions C1-3 are as follows:

- $X_{k-1}(a, b) + \theta_k P_k(a, b) \leq X^*(a, b) \quad \forall a, b \in [n]$ (where n is the dimension of the matrix)
- $\theta_k > 0$
- $\sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i \leq 1$.

Our first result, which we refer to as Result-1, is the following theorem that characterizes the sparsity of general Birkhoff, for the Algorithm presented in Figure 27 and Figure 28. With the following choices of parameters: $\alpha = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_{\min}}{n}}(1 - \sum_{i=1}^k \theta_i)$ and $\mu_{\min} = 1/n^3$, the number of steps required to obtain ϵ -approximation is

$$k \leq 2 \log^{-1} \left(1 - \min_{i \in [k]} \frac{n\theta_i^2}{\|X_{i-1} - X^*\|_F^2} \right)^{-1} \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{n}}{\epsilon} \right)$$

In other words, our first result states that the number of permutations (equivalently, switching actions) needed to obtain any ϵ -approximation increases only logarithmically with $\frac{1}{\epsilon}$. This indicates that the general Birkhoff setup explained earlier can obtain a good approximation with a finite number of switches.

5.2.3.2 Characterizing Frank-Wolf (FW) sparsity

Similar to the previous subsection, we aim to study the required switching actions, via the FW method, to get the ϵ -approximation. This method is the second component in the proposed new algorithm (after Birkhoff), which is to be presented in the following sub-section.

First, we need to rewrite the Birkhoff algorithm of the last section in a vector form (i.e., flattening the doubly stochastic matrix). This is shown in Figure 30. Then, the FW method is characterized by replacing the steps in lines 4-6 with those in Figure 31.

```

1: Input: Birkhoff polytope  $\mathcal{B}$ ,  $x^* \in \mathcal{B}$ ,  $\epsilon \geq 0$ ,  $k_{\max} \geq 1$ 
2: Set:  $k = 1$  and  $x_0 = 0$ 
3: while  $\|x^* - x_{k-1}\|_2 > \epsilon$  and  $k \leq k_{\max}$  do
4:    $p_k \leftarrow \text{LP}(-[x^* - x_{k-1}], \mathcal{B})$ 
5:    $\star \theta_k \leftarrow \text{BIRKHOFF\_STEP}(x^*, x_{k-1}, p_k)$ 
6:    $x_k \leftarrow x_{k-1} + \theta_k p_k$ 
7:    $k \leftarrow k + 1$ 
8: end while
9: return  $(p_1, \dots, p_{k-1}), (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_{k-1})$ 

```

Figure 30. Vectorized form of Birkhoff.

```

2:  $p_k \leftarrow \text{LP}(-(x^* - x_{k-1}), \mathcal{B})$ 
3:  $\theta_k \leftarrow (x^* - x_{k-1})^T (p_k - x_{k-1}) / \|p_k - x_{k-1}\|_2^2$ 
4:  $x_k \leftarrow x_{k-1} + \theta_k (p_k - x_{k-1})$ 

```

Figure 31. Steps characterizing the FW method.

The main difference between the FW method and the vectorized Birkhoff is that FW can be considered as solving the same linear program in line 4 from Figure 30 without the ceiling operation. The implication of this change is that the FW method takes into account the geometry of the decomposition, i.e., how close x_{k-1} is to x_k entry-wise.

Our main result for this observation is the following characterization, which we refer to as Result-2. The Algorithmic steps in Figure 31 obtain an ϵ -approximation after a number of steps k that is upper bounded through $k \leq \frac{4n}{\epsilon^2}$.

The proof is detailed in the publications [35]. Result-2 indicates that we may not be able to obtain a sparse decomposition (i.e., a low number of switching actions) as a result of using the FW method. One of the causes of such behavior is the "zig-zag" property of first-order optimization methods (see, e.g., [36]). Thus, even though FW selects the steepest descent direction, such direction is only good locally, and better improvement is possible by selecting bigger steps but in a more carefully selected direction (i.e., towards x^*).

5.2.3.3 A New algorithm: Birkhoff+

In this section, we present `Birkhoff+`, a variation of the original Birkhoff's algorithm that uses the intuition behind FW to obtain sparse decompositions in a fast manner. This new algorithm is characterized by having to execute the steps in Figure 32 in place of the line annotated with (o) in the vectorized form of Figure 30 shows the intuition behind the proposed algorithm. Generally and roughly speaking, Birkhoff's

algorithm can be seen as creating a path from the origin to a target value, while remaining in the feasible region (dotted region). FW constructs a path from a permutation matrix within the polytope of doubly stochastic matrices (blue surface). The proposed approach can be seen as using FW but within the polytope $\text{conv}(I_k(\alpha) \cup x_{k-1})$, with the additional constraints that the decomposition must be in the feasible region.

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &\leftarrow (1 - \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \theta_i) / n^2 \\ p_k &\leftarrow \text{LP}(\nabla f_\beta(x_{k-1}), \text{conv}(I_k(\alpha))) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 32. Steps for Birkhoff+.

Figure 33. Schematic illustration of the (a) Birkhoff's and (b) Frank-Wolfe approaches and how they combine into the (c) new setup. The yellow polygon represents the convex hull of x_{k-1} and the permutation matrices in $I_k(\alpha)$.

In our third result, Birkhoff+ obtains an ϵ -approximation with at most $k \leq O(\log \frac{1}{\epsilon})$, and operates by solving a single linear program per step (as opposed to multiple such linear programs for methods based on Birkhoff, e.g., [37]). The proof of this result is available in the published work [35].

5.2.4 N-MAPE-K representation

The following table explains how the presented functionality maps on the N-MAPE-K framework.

Table 35. N-MAPE-K representation of efficient backhaul circuit switching.

N-MAPE-K module	Solution module
Sensors	The sensing part of the proposed NIF solution is represented by the traffic sensors in data centers. Such sensors are implemented via API.
Monitor	The NIF accesses the traffic sensors, monitoring for expected intensive data rates, which can be captured via API request pressure monitoring.
Analyze	The analysis part is simply a thresholding mechanism, which is set according to the operation cost and specifications of the adapted circuit switches in the data center.
Plan	The plan step is represented by computing a permutation matrix (which corresponds to computing a circuit switching configuration) according to one of the analyzed algorithms (Birkhoff or FW), or the newly suggested one (Birkhoff +). More specifically, in Birkhoff+, the plan step is solving the linear program specified in Figure 32.
Execute	The execute part of the proposed NIF solution is presented by issuing a command to the control software of the circuit switches with the resulting configuration found in the "plan" step. Recall that this configuration is a part of a chain of configurations that will result in repeating the MAPE-K process. Such a chain has the desired properties of causing the approximation error, defined earlier in the problem description paragraph, to diminish to zero.
Effector	The effector part is the circuit switching mechanism built into the circuits. They automatically modify the wiring configuration through their software-controlled electronics to realize the switching (connections) determined in the last step.

5.2.5 Mapping to major standards (if applicable) and gaps identification

The Open Networking Foundation (ONF) provides ONOS⁹, an SDN controller for programmable networks. Network control algorithms similar to the proposed ones can be programmed through SD-RAN¹⁰, a software suite that is compliant with O-RAN [4] architecture.

⁹ <https://opennetworking.org/onos/>

¹⁰ <https://opennetworking.org/open-ran/>

6 Application of NI-native architecture in WP3 NI solutions

In the native NI architecture described by DAEMON in D2.2 [2], we defined the main components and elements that are used to build the DAEMON's NI plane. Throughout this document, we analyzed the requirements that have been met, the split into the N-MAPE-K representation, and the relevant SDO architecture that are in target for each NI-assisted solution. In this section, we discuss further considerations that stem from the application of the proposed WP2 architecture in the context of the WP3 solutions, which will serve as additional requirements for the architectural work.

6.1 Conflict resolution

Through the split into NIF components, or NIF-C, according to the N-MAPE-K framework proposed in [38], DAEMON's NI Orchestrator shall be able to efficiently re-use and combine different elements that can be shared across NI Functions (NIF) eventually building a NI Service (NIS) analogously to the approach used by 3GPP SA5 to build the Network Slicing data model (i.e., a Network Slice is decomposed into Network Slice subnets and VNFs). However, while composing NIFs to build a NIS, through the sharing of different NIF-Cs, possible conflicts may arise. It is hence a task of the NI Orchestrator to arbitrate the operation of such components, guaranteeing that the overall goal of the NIS is met.

Figure 34. vRAN management Network Intelligent Service (NIS) comprised of two NIFs.

Let us exemplify this behavior by detailing the arrangement of Nuberu and Athena, two NIFs described respectively in Sections 2.1 and 2.5, that aim at improving the resiliency of a vRAN system by acting on MAC scheduling decision at the Distributed Unit (DU) of gNBs. In the case of Nuberu, a re-design of the full stack to be cloud-native and resilient to fluctuation is proposed; in the case of Athena, a model that learns the limits of the infrastructure and takes scheduling decisions accordingly is proposed instead. Hence, several components may be shared among these two NIFs: Sources (the analytics of the Forward Error Coding (FEC) decoder) and Sinks (the MAC scheduler). In this context, different conflicts may arise:

- **Conflicts when monitoring data:** algorithms may need data from the same source with different granularities. For instance, Athena requires decoding times per TB for training, while Nuberu needs information for each decoding iteration of the FEC decoder to understand how to apply early HARQ techniques. The **NIF Manager shall guarantee that the needed information arrives from the Sources to the specific Plan/Analyze modules with the required granularity in an automated manner.**
- **Conflicts in the policy enforcement:** both Nuberu and Athena act on the MAC scheduler, the first one to perform just-in-time scheduling of frames as soon as they are decoded (to include the HARQ information), Athena properly selects the TB size to match the infrastructure. So, the **Intelligent Orchestrator shall deploy, together with the NIF-C of each NIF, also conflict resolution policies** to guarantee that, e.g., the scheduled MAC frame never exceeds the available capacity or contrasting users are selected.

Together with these two requirements, the NI Orchestrator shall also properly monitor the operation of the decisions taken for these two problems (especially for the one on conflict resolution) and possibly amend this decision when suboptimal choices are taken.

6.2 In-backhaul inference and reconfiguration

Figure 35. Co-existence of solutions for automated in-backhaul inference and reconfiguration.

Figure 35 shows how the two solutions developed by DAEMON that operate in backhaul would be represented via N-MAPE-K by the NI Orchestrator. The solutions are described in detail in Section 5.1 and Section 5.2 and aim at performing (i) in-switch inference at line rate and (ii) optimal configuration of circuit switching based on live traffic demands.

The diagrams clearly show how the two solutions are largely disjoint and can thus co-exist in the network system without particular needs for, e.g., conflict resolution, as in the scenario presented in Section 6.1 above. In particular, NIF1, implementing in-switch inference, mostly acts within the user plane, i.e., in programmable switches, and its decisions are applied both to the immediate traffic flow forwarding of the switch and to the longer-timescale forwarding policies determined in the control plane (based on in-switch inference outcome, and driven, e.g., by an ONOS controller). Instead, NIF2, realizing the circuit switching configuration, has the core stages happening in the control plane and decisions enacted in the user plane.

Where the two solutions have points of contact is in the Source and Sink stages. The Source is located in the user plane for both NIF1 and NIF2. Specifically, NIF1 directly ingest the actual IP packets that constitute the traffic in the network, which are then classified individually based on their flow of pertinence. Instead, NIF2 uses information about the traffic volume, which can be generated by the switches themselves from the IP packets above. Therefore, there is a dependency in the Sink stages, with the component of NIF2 actually depending on that of NIF1. In the Sink stages, the actions enacted by NIF1 and NIF2 in the user plane both target the programmable switches, either in terms of immediate forwarding decisions based on the inference outcome or of circuit switching configuration, respectively.

Ultimately, the scenario portrayed in Figure 35 provides a clear example of a situation where two NIFs share both input and output resources. Analogously to Section 6.1, the two solutions require **monitoring coordination**. That is, the two NIFs **shall be granted effective access to the monitoring resources** that ensures, e.g., avoiding the duplication of the monitoring effort over IP packets. This creates a requirement for the NIP and, in particular, for **the NIF Manager that shall be able to control via the NIF-C Manager the flow of information among the components of different NI instances**, especially when the source information may entail exclusive access.

6.3 Model selection

Throughout this document, we listed a number of solutions that build on the knowledge of the underlying environment that could be software (e.g., the decoding times provided by a specific FEC implementation), hardware (the same decoding time may change on the kind or amount of computing resources assigned to that task), or even location-aware (RIS may have different behavior according to their location properties). These tasks, when executed in the context of a pure ML environment, are tackled by several MLOPS frameworks natively. In the context of a NI native architecture, however, this

requires tight interaction with the underlying orchestration environment. As discussed, NI models need to match the specific hardware-software-environmental characteristics of the network functions deployed in a network service to guarantee that the deployed NI Service can operate in the right context. Thus, **the NI Orchestrator shall exchange execution context information with the sibling MANO operating in the network** to be able to select the proper model to be used in inference within a NIF, and if no model is available for the specific execution environment, trigger the training of a specific one, fetching the required data as detailed by the algorithmic solution.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

The present deliverable D3.2 presented the progress of WP3 in the design of ten (10) NI-assisted functionalities that address the respective network problems introduced in D3.1. In addition, this document introduced two new problems (related to RAN virtualization and in-backhaul learning, respectively) and the associated solutions. For each solution, we analyzed the level of satisfaction of the requirements and guidelines devised in WP2 (see D2.2) to design them. We also presented a detailed explanation of each solution and their suitability to standardization bodies. Moreover, following the guidelines of the architectural work in WP2, each NI solution has been represented with the WP2-proposed N-MAPE-K models, which helps to harmonize the analysis and development of these functionalities in addition to identify architectural gaps in WP2.

Jointly with WP4 solutions (see D4.2), all these NI-assisted functionalities pursue Objective 2 in the Grant Agreement and aim at helping meet a wide range of KPIs from Objective 4 in the context of energy savings, OPEX savings, reliability or spectrum efficiency. The presented functionalities are clustered into the respective WP3 tasks: compute-aware radio scheduling, multi-timescale edge resource management, reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, and in-backhaul support for network intelligence.

Though thorough evaluations of these solutions will be performed in WP5, some preliminary validations have been presented in some of the functionalities, which proves that the right path is being followed. For others, such validation will be dutifully presented in D5.2.

Notably, the design of WP3 NI-assisted functionalities has adopted a critical approach toward the use of data-driven models based on neural networks. In fact, a number of solutions have adopted alternative methodologies that are more suitable for practical deployments (e.g., Section 2.1 or Section 4 devise non-data-driven methods that are amenable to real-time sub-millisecond-level operation).

We concluded this deliverable by analyzing a set of new requirements that stem from the work in WP3. More specifically, we have uncovered the need for conflict resolution approaches, monitoring coordination methods, and meta-intelligence for appropriate model selection at the NI plane perspective. This serves as WP3 feedback for the architectural work carried out in the context of WP2.

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